

**HOW THREE EUROPEAN
REGIONS GOVERNED
ECONOMIC TRANSITIONS:**

LESSONS FROM

SOUTHEAST NORTH BRABANT (NL),

CLUJ COUNTY (RO),

& BASQUE COUNTRY (ES)

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1. INTRODUCTION

By signing the Paris Climate Agreement, governments worldwide have committed to achieving climate neutrality by 2050. This ambitious goal necessitates a deep and systemic restructuring of both the economy and society, touching almost every aspect of our lives, from energy production and transportation to agriculture, industry, and urban planning. Given the scale and complexity of the transformation, achieving this within the limited time frame presents a significant challenge. Unlike more gradual economic and societal shifts, the urgency of climate change requires a rapid, coordinated, and multi-level approach, making it paramount to draw lessons from past transitions to navigate this process.

History offers several examples of large-scale transformations that reshaped economies, societies, and governance structures. The transition from an industrial to a post-industrial economy led to widespread job losses, the decline of traditional manufacturing hubs, and the emergence of new economic centers focused on services, technology, and finance. This shift drastically altered regional economic landscapes, particularly in parts of Europe where deindustrialization left lasting social and economic scars. Similarly, the transition from a socialist planned economy to a market economy in Eastern Europe in the 1990s required not only economic liberalization but also extensive legal and institutional changes. Entire industries collapsed, ownership structures were overhauled, and millions of people had to adjust to new labor market conditions, often without adequate social protection. More recently, the financial crisis of 2008 exposed deep vulnerabilities in global financial systems, forcing cities and regions to reinvent themselves, adopt new governance frameworks, and implement austerity or stimulus measures to regain stability.

Although the current transition to a climate-neutral economy is primarily driven by the need to protect the environment—whereas economic or political imperatives often prompted previous transitions—their trajectories provide valuable insights into the dynamics of systemic change. They reveal how policy choices shape who benefits from transitions and who bears the costs. Government intervention, institutional frameworks, and power dynamics among economic actors all influence whether transitions exacerbate inequalities or create opportunities for inclusive well-being for all. By analyzing past experiences, policymakers can better anticipate social disruptions, mitigate unintended consequences, and design transition strategies that are both effective and inclusive. That is the reason this report investigates three regions in Europe that underwent economic and social transitions in the past: Southeast North Brabant (NL), Cluj County (RO), and Basque Country (ES). This report offers valuable lessons from the regions for the current climate transition.

Aim of the project

The BOLSTER project examines regions currently undergoing significant economic transformations due to the European Union’s policy to achieve a Just Transition, which fosters the shift toward a carbon-neutral economy. This policy requires the decarbonization of polluting industries such as coal, steel, cement, chemicals, and fossil fuel. Historically, these industries have been concentrated in specific European regions, which are now strongly affected. The European Commission, therefore, created the Just Transition Fund (JTF) to deal with the socio-economic effects of the climate transition. Regions must design Territorial Just Transition Plans (TJTJs) to be eligible for funding from the JTF. While the transition to a carbon-neutral economy is essential in combating climate change, it also brings significant challenges, particularly for workers in carbon-intensive industries and the communities whose livelihoods depend on them.

Therefore, the adoption of the Just Transition presents one of the toughest socio-economic dilemmas for European regions. On the one hand, these regions must restructure and scale down entire industrial sectors, diversify their economies, and ensure decent employment opportunities for workers and communities reliant on these industries. On the other hand, the transition must be done in a just way, ensuring that the most vulnerable populations are not disproportionately impacted. This necessarily requires the inclusion of diverse population groups in the governance of the transition process.

In this project, we focus on the former challenge: how to govern the economic transition while ensuring people retain jobs and maintain their quality of life. Governments alone cannot manage such a substantial shift and therefore urgently seek successful strategies to bring together relevant actors and create a strong governance coalition to support economic diversification.

As described above, this project contributes by studying three regions that have undergone transitions similar to those currently faced by Just Transition Regions. The regions examined are Southeast North Brabant (NL), Cluj County (RO), and the Basque Country (ES). These regions were selected based on four criteria:

1. They have experienced the closure of industries that were once central to their economies.
2. The transition was deemed ‘successful’ based on the macroeconomic indicators such as GDP.
3. They are peripheral regions located outside of their national capitals, where economic and political power is usually concentrated.
4. They represent diverse European contexts from the North, East, and South, respectively.

The guiding research questions are as follows:

- What do governance networks in the ‘economically successful’ transition regions look like?
- What socio-spatial implications do the ‘economically successful’ transitions bring along? Or to what extent do governance processes of transitions transform social structures and urban spaces?

About the report

This report provides a comprehensive analysis based on data collected from three study regions between June 2023 and February 2024. The data come from official policy documents and qualitative interviews with key stakeholders involved in the governance of the transition, accounting actors excluded from the process and representatives of communities considered marginalized or vulnerable in their national contexts. A total of 55 interviews were conducted, including 23 in North Brabant, 21 in Cluj County, and 11 in the Basque Country. Researchers visited each of these regions to carry out fieldwork, and most interviews were conducted in person.

This report is intended for policymakers and other actors involved in the implementation of regional transitions. Thus, it offers practical insights aimed at inspiring and informing actors working on the ground, highlighting best practices from each of the three regions, as well as some challenges and negative implications.

The report is structured around three broader themes:

I. Governance networks:

- Who are the governing actors, and how do they come together to form governance networks for transitions?
- Who is included and excluded from these networks?

II. Governance and policy-making processes:

- What role do different sectors (or helices)—private, governmental, educational, and civil society—play in governing the transition?
- What new organizations emerge to govern between these helices?
- How do different governance levels (supranational, national, regional, local) affect the policymaking process?

III. Emerging vulnerabilities:

- What social, socio-economic, political, cultural, or spatial vulnerabilities emerge in the transition regions and what challenges do they present for governance?

2. THREE REGIONS AT A GLANCE

In this report we focus on three diverse regions that have gone through an economically successful transition in the past. In terms of the geographical borders, initially, our entry point was to focus on NUTS 3: small regions, according to the EU classification known as Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS). NUTS 3 regions are Southeast North Brabant (Zuidoost-Noord-Brabant in Dutch) in the Netherlands with the capital city of Eindhoven, Cluj in Romania with the capital city Cluj-Napoca, and Bizkaia in Spain with the capital city of Bilbao. However, in practice, in the Spanish case, the regional borders where the governance measures were applied were larger than NUTS 3 and corresponded to NUTS 2 level - Basque Country, which included three NUTS 3 provinces: Bizkaia, Gipuzkoa, and Araba. In the Dutch case, the region under study is referred to as the Brainport region, named after the triple-helix governance body. Brainport region has started within the borders of Southeast North Brabant (NUTS 3), but in recent years it has been expanding to include two other NUTS 3 provinces of Central North Brabant (with the capital in Tilburg), and West North Brabant (with the capital in Breda). As a result, it has recently been corresponding more to NUTS 2 - North Brabant, with the exception for Northeast North Brabant region, which is not included in the Brainport. But since this expansion is very recent, we will mainly refer to the original borders of the Brainport region within the Southeast Brabant. In Romanian case, the region where the transition governance measures were applied correspond to the initially selected NUTS 3 region - Cluj County. Below on Table 1 we provide key regional characteristics in a comparative perspective and after that introduce each region at a glance.

	SOUTHEAST NORTH BRABANT, THE NETHERLANDS (NUTS 3)	CLUJ COUNTY, ROMANIA (NUTS 3)	BASQUE COUNTRY, SPAIN (NUTS 2)
Geographical area (km²)	1.440	6.674	7.234
Population number for 2022	Largest City - Eindhoven: 238.307 Region: 791.075 Source: CBS ¹	Largest City - Cluj-Napoca: 286.598 Region: 679.141 Source: INS ²	Largest City - Bilbao: 340.455 Region: 2.186.517 Source: Eustat.eus ³
Administrative divisions	21 municipalities	5 municipalities, 1 city, and 75 communes Source: INS ⁴	3 provinces and 251 municipalities
Population trajectory	Steady growth	Periodical decline	Modest growth (declining natural population with positive migratory balance)
GDP per capita	2013: 7.8 % 2023: 3.4% Source: CBS ⁵	2013: 39.3 mii RON 2023: 124 mii RON (equals to 24.826 euro) Source: Zf.ro ⁶	2015: 31.811 euro 2023: 42.058 euro Source: Eustat.eus ⁷
Unemployment rate	2013: 7.8 % 2023: 3.4% Source: CBS ⁸	2013: 7.6% 2024: 1.16% Source: ZCJ. RO ⁹ and ANOFM ¹⁰	2013: 16.6% 2024: 7.1% Source: Datosmacro.com ¹¹ & Eustat.eus ¹²
Former economic base	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Agriculture ▪ Lightning, electronics, and engineering (led by Philips) ▪ Automobile production (led by DAF) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Chemical industry, Ceramics, ▪ Wood, ▪ Leather, ▪ Heavy machinery and automobile industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Steel industry ▪ Machine tools ▪ Automobiles ▪ Home appliances
Emerging economic base	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Semiconductor industry (led by ASML and NXP) ▪ Electronics and robotics, especially in healthcare sector such as MRI, CT and ultrasound scanners (led by Philips) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ICT sector (software development and IT outsourcing) ▪ Automotive ▪ Agribusiness ▪ Chemical and pharmaceutical industries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable energy ▪ Aerospace and automotive industries ▪ Biotechnology
Innovation development	The Province of North Brabant is positioned in top category of the Regional Innovation Index (2023) with the score of 140.8 . Source: European Commission ¹³	Together with all Romanian regions, Nord-Vest region where Cluj County is located is in the lowest category of the Regional Innovation Index. With the score of 37.4 , it positions among the bottom 10 weakest innovation regions in Europe. Source: European Commission ¹⁴	Basque Country is positioned in the second highest category of the Regional Innovation Index (2023) with the score of 119.1 . Source: European Commission ¹⁵

Southeast North Brabant, the Netherlands

Southeast North Brabant is a region in the southern Netherlands with a population of 791,075. It comprises 21 municipalities, the largest of which are Eindhoven (the regional capital), Helmond, and Veldhoven. The region has shown steady growth in both population and economic development. Historically, it was known for its strong manufacturing industry, led by companies like Philips and DAF. Today, the region is recognized for its high-tech, design, and advanced manufacturing industries. The headquarters of global semiconductor industry leaders, ASML and NXP, are located here. The region is now renowned for its innovation output and high patent creation rates. According to the Regional Innovation Index (2023), the Province of North Brabant, with its dominant cluster in Southeast North Brabant, is classified as one of Europe's strongest innovation leaders. Philips was founded in Eindhoven in 1891 by Gerard Philips and his father, Frederik, initially focusing on producing light bulbs. Over the course of the 20th century, Philips grew into one of the world's largest electronics conglomerates, achieving global market dominance with a wide range of products, including kitchen appliances, electric shavers, televisions, cassettes, compact discs, and, of course, light bulbs. Philips was founded in Eindhoven in 1891 by Gerard Philips and his father, Frederik, initially focusing on producing light bulbs. Over the course of the 20th century, Philips grew into one of the world's largest electronics conglomerates, achieving global market dominance with a wide range of products, including kitchen appliances, electric shavers, televisions, cassettes, compact discs, and, of course, light bulbs.

One of our informants from Eindhoven remembers: *“Everybody knows Philips because they had something at home, which was from Phillips, like a radio, or a television, or a CD, or a cassettebandje [In Dutch for cassette tape].”* (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023).

At its peak, the company also held a prominent position in the entertainment industry. However, fierce competition from East Asian rivals in the 1990s and 2000s led to significant downsizing, including the sale of its lighting and consumer electronics divisions. This marked Philips' transformation into a healthcare-focused company, as it operates today. Philips is fondly remembered as a family-owned company that provided stable, secure conditions for its employees and cared not only for its workers but also for their families. One former Philips employee recalls:

“I think Phillips workers were spoiled [laughing]. It was a very social company. [...] Because we had everything there, like sports clubs and medical support, everything. Everything was centered around Philips. [...] And when you had children that studied, because by that time my children were going to college. There were funds for children that studied, and they each got, like, €200 a month, I think during their study. So, they had support from Phillips.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

Later adding: *“[...] You know, because when you work here, you're secure for the rest of your life. That's what his father told him when he was 14: 'If you get a job at Phillips, don't ever leave. Yeah, stay there until you're a pensioner.'”* (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

Figure 1. The city of Eindhoven. Source: Authors

Philips is also known for its diverse departments, where each was a self-sufficient entity and eventually resulted in many spinoffs. For example, in 1998, Philips created a semiconductors unit, which spun off as NXP in 2006. ASML, now the world's largest photolithography producer of computer chips, was also a spinoff of Philips. As well as Signify, which spun off from Philips's lighting division in 2016. Philips spinoffs have not only flourished and emerged as industry leaders but have also far surpassed the parent company in value creation.

Philips' NatLab (Figure 2), the company's renowned research department, conducted both fundamental and product-specific research. NatLab was famously referred to as a “superuniversity,” where the best and brightest could conduct research under ideal conditions—enjoying full academic freedom, minimal administrative burdens, and nearly unlimited budgets.¹⁶

Figure 2. Former Philips NatLab Building, now a movie theatre. Source: Authors

DAF, founded in 1932 by brothers Hub and Wim Van Doorne, grew from a small mechanical workshop into a major manufacturer of trucks and cars. The company's headquarters and main factory are located in Eindhoven. DAF was a pioneer in the production of trucks, buses, and trailers, boasting a fully integrated production line. In 1993, the company declared bankruptcy but was subsequently relaunched on a smaller scale as DAF Trucks N.V. In 1996, it was acquired by the American company Paccar.

During the industrial crisis, the region experienced a drastic decline. Between 1990 and 1996, Philips laid off 55,000 employees worldwide, including around 8,000 in Southeast North Brabant (ibid.). In 1993, DAF went bankrupt and had to lay off nearly half of its workforce before downsizing to a smaller company. Many suppliers of these two companies also faced crises.

At the peak of the crisis, the government, private companies, and educational institutions joined forces to drive the region's economic reinvention.¹⁷ This three-party collaboration, known as the Triple Helix, was named Brainport. The legacy of the past shaped the region's transition from a traditional industrial area to a hub of high-tech and design industries. In 2004, Southeast North Brabant was officially designated as a national 'Brainport' by the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs, alongside two other key areas: Amsterdam Schiphol Airport and the Port of Rotterdam, which opened access to larger financial investments from the national government. Initially, the triple-helix 'Brainport' had no formal structure and operated through programs and projects, with the most successful ones being Stimulus (1990) and Horizon (2001). In 2005, the Brainport Foundation was formally established to lead the Brainport Programs, which focuses on technology valorization and, more broadly, on economic and social development toward a high quality of life in the region.¹⁸

Cluj County, Romania

Cluj County is located in the northwest of Romania, with a population of 679,141. Its capital, Cluj-Napoca, with a population of 286,598, serves as the main cultural and religious center of Transylvania, a historic and multicultural region nestled between the Carpathian and Apuseni Mountains. Cluj County comprises 5 municipalities, 1 city (Huedin), and 75 communes, including Florești, a commune with the second-largest population after Cluj-Napoca, totaling 52,735. You will see the name of Florești in chapter *Specific to Cluj County: growing urban-rural divide and discrimination towards Roma communities*, where we explore the urban-rural divide in Cluj Region.

Figure 3. The city of Cluj-Napoca. Source: Authors

The population in Cluj has experienced periodic decline. Between 1995 and 2005, it shrank, but since 2005, it has begun to grow again. Over the last 20 years, Cluj County's population trajectory has been described as "an island of population growth in a sea of shrinkage", given Romania's overall population decline due to low birth rates and significant outmigration to Western Europe and the UK. Historically, Cluj has been a multi-ethnic region. According to a study using 2011 census data, Cluj County is home to 75% Romanians, 15% Hungarians, and 3% Roma.^{19, 20} The economy of Cluj County is steadily growing. According to data from the National Strategy and the Forecasting Commission (CNSP) presented in Presshub publication, since 2013, its GDP per capita has tripled. As of 2023, the GDP per capita in Cluj County is one of the highest in the country, at 24,826 euros, significantly higher than the national average of 13,129 euros.²¹

The industrial decline of the 1990s in Cluj coincided with the fall of the Soviet regime and a political crisis. Between 1992 and 2004, the city was impacted by discriminating policies of its mayor, Gheorghe Funar, who was known for his nationalist views and oppressive actions against non-ethnic Romanian communities. This period was marked by "protectionism toward the local economy."²² After 2004, with the election of the new liberal-democratic mayor, Emil Boc, Cluj began to evolve into the "regional center for the transnationalization of the Romanian economy."²³ This political shift aligned with the globalization of outsourcing operations, attracted to the city after financial crisis of 2008. As a result, the Cluj region succeeded in four transnational fields: Information & Communications Technology, Business Support Services, Engineering, Research & Development, and Financial Services.²⁴

Since the 2000th, Cluj has been known for its booming ICT sector, often referred in media as Silicon Valley of Eastern Europe.²⁵ However, in comparison to the Brainport region, who is leading in intellectual property and patent creation, Cluj region has registered "its weakest performance."²⁶ In the period analyzed by the European Commission, the city registered only 3.32 patent applications and only 2.85 applications were developed for the community (per 100.000 people).²⁷ This ranking shows the specificity of the local market, characterized by outsourcing, especially in IT services and innovation.²⁸ Our interviews revealed that innovation activities and patents are being created in Cluj locally but for parent international companies. Intellectual property laws arrange that locally produced innovations are registered at the country of the parent company. This effectively explains the low number of patents registered in the region. The large share of ICT in outsourcing services also puts Cluj ICT sector in precarious position because the parent companies can leave to other countries like it has previously happened with Nokia, when the Finish company closed down its factory in Cluj after only 3 years of operations to move to East Asia.²⁹ This closure explained by the financial crisis of 2008-2009, has led to 2,200 people losing their jobs.

Figure 4. The city of Cluj-Napoca. Source: Authors

Basque Country, Spain

The Basque Country, the largest of the three regions, is an autonomous community in northern Spain. The region consists of three large provinces, Biscay, Araba, and Gipuzkoa, which together comprise 251 municipalities. The natural population of the region has been steadily shrinking over the last decade, due to the drastically declining birth rates. For this reason, the aging population is also accelerating. However, positive migratory balances compensate for natural population decline, and overall, the region's population remains steady and slightly growing.

The largest city, Bilbao, located in the province of Biscay, stands as a testament to both its industrial past and its modern reinvention. Historically, the Basque Country's economy was grounded in agriculture. However, during the industrialization period, the region became one of the first in Spain to adopt technological innovations, and its steel industry emerged as a central pillar of its economic development, securing its position as a leader in industrial advancement.³⁰

Figure 5. The city of Bilbao. Source: Authors

The Spanish Civil War (1936–1939) brought harsh changes to the Basque Country. The Basque Statute of Autonomy, known as the Statute of Gernika, was abolished, and economic agreements in Biscay and Gipuzkoa were revoked due to the region's support for the Republicans. Despite these setbacks, the Basque economy proved resilient, building on established industries while expanding into new sectors like machine tools, automobiles, and home appliances.³¹

From 1936 to 1959, Spain's autarky period stifled technological innovation and foreign investment, limiting progress in the Basque industrial sector. The Basque people faced economic hardship, political repression, and social restrictions. Trade unions were banned, wages stagnated despite soaring inflation, and families relied on rationing cards and the black market to survive. In 1940, the Spanish government began suppressing cultural expressions, including the Basque language, fueling anti-centralist and anti-Spanish sentiments. These tensions eventually led to the rise of the terrorist group Euskadi Ta Askatasuna (ETA), a group that played a major role in the region's turbulent history.³²

The 1973 oil crisis and Franco's death in 1975 brought political instability and a transitional period as Spain moved toward democracy. The approval of the Spanish Constitution in 1978 marked a turning point, with new democratic institutions emerging nationwide. In the Basque Country, this era saw social unrest, including massive strikes and a revived labor movement after nearly 40 years of dictatorship. Unemployment in the Basque provinces surged from

2.4% in 1975 to 23.8% by the mid-1980s, reflecting the struggles of the region's traditional industrial base amid broader economic changes.³³

However, by the 1990s, the Basque Country entered a period of economic reorganization. A strategic shift towards the service sector began to take root, and the importance of services in the regional GDP grew steadily. As industrial spaces became more limited, Bilbao underwent a dramatic transformation with the completion of the Guggenheim Museum in 1997.

In recent years, the Basque Country has emerged as a hub of innovation, driven by advanced manufacturing, renewable energy, digital technologies, and biotechnology. This transformation is underpinned by a strong commitment to research and development, with the region consistently investing around 2% of its GDP in R&D—one of the highest rates in Spain.³⁴ Besides, the region has also been one of the leaders in per capita return of European funds. For instance, between 2021 and 2022, it attracted 240 million euros.³⁵

Figure 6. Guggenheim Bilbao Museum.
Source: Authors

3. MULTI-HELIX GOVERNANCE MODEL OF INNOVATION

Governance models provide frameworks for organizing interactions and decision-making among different societal actors to achieve specific objectives. For instance, traditional top-down models focus on centralized authority and hierarchical structures to regulate economic and social systems. Collaborative governance models, on the other hand, are designed to foster cooperative decision-making processes, ensuring that different groups of actors are engaged, including public, private, and different civil society groups. These models adapt to ever-changing conditions in the economy, politics, society, and environment, changing their governance practices. In this chapter, we focus on the multi-helix governance model, which is present in all three regions, and was established primarily to govern innovations, technology, and knowledge. This model is specifically tailored to drive a knowledge- and innovation-based economy by facilitating collaboration between the three helices—university, industry, and government—also known as the Triple Helix.

The concept of the Triple Helix was co-developed by Henry Etzkowitz and Loet Leydesdorff in the early 1990s.³⁶ While both scholars contributed to the foundational ideas, Etzkowitz is often associated with further advancing and popularizing the model, particularly through his seminal book 'The Triple Helix: University-Industry-Government Innovation in Action,' published in 2008. In this book, Etzkowitz clearly brings across the purpose of the model - "the restructuring and enhancement of the organizational arrangements and incentives that foster innovation."³⁷ He highlights that this new governance model is necessary because "knowledge moves from the periphery to the center of industrial production and governance"³⁸ and transforms the concept of innovation, as it was understood in the industrial economy.

The studies on the multi-helix model, including those mentioned above, often overlook critical questions regarding its democratic validity and social justice implications. To address these gaps, we highlight three key points that are discussed in this study while also inviting further discussion:

1. **Balancing roles:** How can the roles of universities, industry, and government be balanced? Particularly with the proliferation of private capital's influence on public policies, what public governance tools and instruments can help avoid asymmetry that hinders the balance?
2. **Social impact:** Does the model adequately address the social consequences of innovation, such as inequality or exclusion? The triple helix is often critiqued for prioritizing economic growth and technological advancement without sufficiently addressing how these innovations impact vulnerable populations or exacerbate inequalities.
3. **Civic inclusion:** With the participatory turn in planning and policy, a big debate appears around whether the model should expand to include civil society as a fourth helix (Quadruple Helix). If so, how can civil society participate in the development of innovations? How can diverse groups of civil society collaborate together to represent the civil society as one helix?

In this section of the report, we aim to shed light on these debates. First, we explore how the multi-helix governance is applied in practice in the three case study regions. We draw governance models presenting organizations that emerge to foster collaborations between helices. Second, we explore what role each of the helices plays in each of the regions.

One of the key findings of BOLSTER project is that civil society groups are still largely excluded from participation in policymaking in the regions undergoing a transition to a knowledge economy. The multi-helix governance structures are mostly focused on innovation and producing specialized knowledge. Societal concerns are often secondary to economic concerns. This also becomes clear in the specific type of policy language spoken between actors in the Triple-Helix network. This language reflects the technical language of engineers and or start-ups, but not the communities of civil society.

Multi-Helix governance models in three regions

In this section we explore how the governance structures of the transitions look like in three regions. We draw governance cartographies to present organizations that play crucial role in the economic transitions. We will pay particular attention to the new organizations set up specifically to govern (or more precisely execute policies) in-between helices.

Southeast North Brabant or 'Brainport' region

Among the three regions under study, the governance structure of the Brainport region is the most complex to map (see Figure 7). Unlike Cluj County and the Basque Country, where the development of innovation transition policies and strategies is spearheaded by specific governmental units—such as the economic or employment department of the regional government or city council — the Brainport region has a formal governance body that integrates individuals from the public, private, and education sectors, comprising a Triple-Helix model. The Brainport Foundation was initially formed in 1995 when the then-mayor of Eindhoven, the President of the Chamber of Commerce, and the President of TU Eindhoven joined forces to transition the region from industrial decline to an innovation-driven economy.³⁹ At that time, the collaboration was informal and lacked a defined structure.

In 2005, the Brainport Foundation was formally established, adopting a more complex and inclusive structure with additional representatives from the private, public, and educational sectors. As of early 2025, the Brainport Foundation comprises 15 non-elected members.

- 1 director of the Brainport Foundation’s executive agency, Brainport Development N.V.,
- 5 representatives of public sector (including 4 mayors of largest municipalities and 1 regional governmental agency for the city region of Eindhoven, Metropoolregio Eindhoven),
- 4 representatives of educational sector,
- 5 representatives of business sector (including 1 research-industry center, TNO).

Notably, the composition of representatives evolves based on the standing and relevance of their respective organizations within the governance or market landscape.

Government

The government sector in the Brainport structure is represented by the Mayor of the Municipality of Eindhoven, who is also the Chairman of the Eindhoven Metropolitan Region, three majors of smaller municipalities in the region, Helmond, Best and Veldhoven, as well as a member of the Executive Board of Metropoolregio Eindhoven, a regional governmental agency for the city region comprising of 21 municipalities, which deals with cross-border issues regarding the environment, spatial planning, and heritage.

Universities

The Brainport representatives from the educational sector include the Chairpersons of the Executive Boards of Eindhoven University of Technology, Fontys University of Applied Sciences, and Tilburg University (see Figure 8). Additionally, Summa College plays a significant role. Summa College comprises 26 secondary vocational schools that are instrumental in training skilled workers for large companies like ASML and NXP. The campuses of Fontys and Summa College are strategically located on the technological and industrial campuses, aligning education closely with the industry needs.

Recently, the Brainport Region expanded its boundaries to include two additional major cities in North Brabant: Breda and Tilburg. Consequently, Tilburg University and Avans University of Applied Sciences in Breda have been incorporated into the Brainport region's educational network. Interestingly, despite its prestige, the Design Academy Eindhoven—a renowned art university—is not featured on the Brainport's map.

New types of organization in-between helices

Brainport Development B.V. is an executive agency of the Brainport Foundation, which deals with the economic development of the region. It was established in 2006. The core tasks of the agency include developing regional economic strategy, stimulating an open ecosystem that leads innovation development, business advice and financing for startups and SMEs, talent attraction and retention, as well as support to the labor market with re-skilling and balancing employment opportunities.

The budget of the Brainport Development consists of two major parts: 1) the 'structural basic financing' that supports the sustainability of the organizations, including for instance, agency's staff, IT, HR services (this funding is provided by the five shareholders of the Brainport Foundation: Metropoolregio Eindhoven, and the municipalities of Eindhoven, Helmond, Veldhoven and Best); and 2) the 'incidental financing' or co-financing from private, provincial, national and European funds. A large part of the second funding source comes from the private sector. In 2023, the total budget of the Brainport Development was 13.140 million euro, where the structural basic financing accounted to 5.64 million euros, and the incidental financing - to 7.5 million.⁴⁰

In the past, the agency was focused predominantly on the governance of knowledge, innovations, and technology, and even though it still remains one of the core focuses, the projects go beyond it. The priorities of the agency also concern 'broad prosperity', which means socio-economic development and wellbeing. Within this broad prosperity, Brainport Development aims to open up its structure to civil society and transform into quadruple helix.⁴¹ Because of this ambition, the project 'Samen voor Eindhoven' (Together for Eindhoven) was set up, which tries to provide support for civil society organizations, debt prevention, as well as development of digital and language skills to participate in the labor market.⁴² However, the project 'Samen voor Eindhoven' is largely targeted towards the employees of the business companies within the innovation network (as, for instance, in the debt prevention and language learning projects). The project appears to cater exclusively to civil society organizations and individuals engaged in technology and innovation while excluding those outside these domains.

Campuses

Technological or industrial campuses in the digital economy are specialized areas that foster collaboration and knowledge exchange between businesses, research institutions, and government bodies. They often provide infrastructure and resources tailored to the needs of tech startups and established companies. By clustering digital economy actors, these campuses aim to drive innovation, accelerate product development, and strengthen the overall tech ecosystem in a region.

The High-Tech Campus, often referred to as the "smartest square kilometer of Europe,"⁴³ is a leading innovation hub and a key driver of the region's high-tech economy. Established as the successor to Philips NatLab, the campus hosts around 300 companies and institutions, ranging from educational institutions like Fontys to startups to global tech giants like ASML, fostering collaboration in fields such as AI, photonics, and nanotechnology. The campus belongs to the American investment company Oaktree Capital Management.

Strijp-S/T, once the industrial heart of Philips, has transformed into a vibrant hub for design, digital technology, and smart solutions. Home to knowledge institutes and large companies like Philips, Bosch, Amazon, Gibson, Strijp-S/T fosters collaboration between tech startups, established firms, and the creative industry. With its industrial heritage repurposed into dynamic workspaces and cultural venues, Strijp-S/T also has a residential area, public spaces, and leisure facilities.

The Brainport Industries Campus (BIC) was conceived in 2014 when the provincial government approved its zoning plan. Today, it stands as the region's leading production campus, bringing together companies that represent the entire high-tech supply chain. Next to the high-tech supply chain, it also houses educational institutions that provide on-site training opportunities for students who work on the machines of private companies. The campus belongs to the British investment firm Capreon; however, in January 2025, the news appeared about its plan to sell the campus and offered it for sale to the municipality of Eindhoven.⁴⁴ The municipality has announced its intention to buy Brainport Industries Campus, which emphasizes the importance of public involvement in the innovation ecosystem.

Automotive Campus is a collaborative space to develop and promote automotive technologies and solutions focused on smart & green mobility. It is located in Helmond and hosts several educational institutions, governmental institutions, large firms like VDL, Delta Electronics, as well as startups.

Private companies

ASML is a global leader in semiconductor manufacturing equipment and the only supplier of Extreme Ultraviolet (EUV) lithography machines, which are essential for producing the smallest and most advanced semiconductors (or simply, chips). Originating in 1984 as a joint venture between Philips and ASMI, ASML overcame early challenges through bold investments in research and development, leading to revolutionary breakthroughs with its EUV machines, capable of printing transistors at a scale smaller than DNA strands. ASML's success is underpinned by substantial R&D funding, strategic acquisitions, and an extensive network of 5,000 supplier partnerships. Despite its monopoly on EUV technology, ASML faces the challenge of meeting skyrocketing global demand as countries push for localized semiconductor production. It is the largest employer in the region, hiring about 250 people per month, many of which are highly skilled migrants.⁴⁵

SIGNIFY, formerly Philips Lighting, is a leading global lighting company specialized in connected LED lighting. The company's focus on sustainable lighting technology, particularly in the Internet of Things (IoT) space, helps drive innovation and supports the local economy by fostering technological advancements and creating high-tech jobs.

NXP Semiconductors spun off from Philips in 2006. Now, it is a global leader in the semiconductor industry, specializing in automotive, IoT, and mobile applications. The company plays a significant role by driving innovation in fields such as connected cars, secure transactions, and smart devices.⁴⁶

Philips, once a major global player in consumer electronics and technology, has scaled down its operations in recent years, focusing on medical devices, health systems, and personal health products. While no longer as dominant in consumer electronics, Philips remains integral to the Eindhoven region, maintaining a significant presence in the local economy through R&D and strategic partnerships.

Educational helix

- Avans University of Applied Sciences
- Fontys University of Applied Sciences
- Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e)
- Tilburg University
- Summa College

Private helix

- ASML
- NXP Semiconductors
- Signify
- Philips
- TNO
- VDL

Public helix

- Eindhoven Municipality
- Helmond Municipality
- Best Municipality
- Veldhoven Municipality
- Metropoolregio Eindhoven (regional governmental agency)

In-between helices organizations

- Brainport Development B.V.

Ecosystem Infrastructure

- The High-Tech Campus
- Strijp-S/T
- The Brainport Industries Campus (BIC)
- Automotive Campus
- TU/e Campus
- Eindhoven Airport

Cluj County

Contrasting to the Brainport, in Cluj, the governance structure to boost the economy looks the least complex of all three regions. This is due to the limited government’s regulatory capacity, which stimulates business and civil society sectors to act more actively. Only a few organizations of new governance structures were developed.

Government

The government sector in Cluj County is represented by the Mayor and the City Council of Cluj-Napoca. However, according to the Digital Transformation Strategy, adopted in 2022, the government's role in digital transition in the region is significantly restricted by the "the lack of qualified personnel, the difficulty of offering a salary package at the market level, the organizational and internal procedures not correlated with the needs of digitalization, as well as the limited inter-departmental cooperation."⁴⁷ During our research in Cluj in 2023, when addressing questions related to the ICT transition, we were consistently referred to two individuals who were regarded as the primary points of contact for this topic. This might suggest a reliance on specific personnel rather than a broader institutional framework or system for the development of the ecosystem.

Universities

The Cluj County is home to the largest number of universities (11, of which 6 public and 5 private) among the three regions under study. The crucial universities are:

Babeş-Bolyai University - the largest Romanian university with approximately 50,000 students, offering study programs in Romanian, Hungarian, German, English, and French (besides a few Master programs taught in Spanish, Italian, and Japanese⁴⁸).

The Technical University of Cluj-Napoca is the second largest university after Babeş-Bolyai. Technical University played a crucial role in training engineers, coders, technicians, and entrepreneurs who formed the IT community in Cluj.

Other universities (presented on Figure 11) include University of Medicine and Pharmacy 'Iuliu Hațieganu'; The University of Agricultural Science and Veterinary Medicine; University of Art and Design; The National Academy of Music 'Gheorghe Dima'; Sapientia Hungarian University; Informal School of IT, University Bogdan Voda Cluj-Napoca; 'Dimitrie Cantemir' Christian University, and Avram Iancu University of Cluj-Napoca.

New types of organizations related to multi-helix governance structures

Center for Imagination and Civic Innovation (CIIC) was founded in 2017 with the idea to create space where civil society, the business ecosystem, and universities can participate in public projects before the stage of their feasibility evaluation. The CIIC has become a space, "in which we can tackle, and we can debate, and we can fight, and we can contradict" (Interview, Cluj, 2023). The idea and realization of CIIC went in parallel with a democratic awakening in Cluj, however in reality the Center's goals were not fully realized. According to research project 'Our Cluj', the Centre was under-funded; lacked long-term approach to urban planning, and was managed by a single employee, which significantly restricted its capacities. Besides, even though the residents appreciated the desire and management abilities of the government to provide the space for participation, the process was hindered by the lack of trust towards public authorities.⁴⁹ According to one of our interviews, the pandemic disturbed the Center's focus and goals.

The Urban Innovation Unit (UIU) is an initiative of the Cluj Cultural Center, a non-governmental organization for culture and sustainable development. The center started in 2018 in partnership with the Municipality's Center for Innovation and Civic Imagination (CIIC) to stimulate collaboration between the multi-helices. Their strategy is to use culture as a catalyst of change. Over the years of its active operation, UIU have collected ideas, knowledge, and resources from civil society organizations, academia, the cultural sector, the business sector as well as the public administration that serve to propose alternative solutions to the strategic challenges of the city in three domains: urban mobility, urban resilience and future of work.⁵⁰ In 2021, the transferring strategy have been developed to transfer UIU to the Cluj-Napoca Municipality (CIIC)⁵¹. In 2022, the transfer process was supposed to be completed. However, the transfer has never happened. According to our

data, which was not first-hand, "when they should have transferred it to the City Hall, then they suddenly met a lot of not noninterest." For the moment, this organization no longer exists.

Private companies

De'Longhi is an Italian manufacturer of household appliances like coffee machines. It has three production facilities in Romania, including one in the village of Jucu, in Cluj County.⁵² The local factory was founded in 2012 to produce espresso machines and later hand mixers. Currently it is the largest producer of coffee machines in Europe, and employs over 2,400 employees. Almost all the employees there are Romanian.⁵³

Bosch Automotive in Cluj has been producing high-quality automotive components and innovative solutions at the Cluj factory, including electronic control units for driver assistance, traffic safety, comfort, and advanced electrification, as well as eBike drive systems. In 2012 the factory expanded in production and logistics and the implementation of energy efficiency measures. Besides the factory, Bosch also has its Bosch Engineering Center in Cluj. With expertise in software, hardware, mechanical engineering, reliability engineering, and sales planning, the center plays a key role in developing innovative products and services leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) in the areas of automated driving, electric mobility, and connected mobility.⁵⁴ Over the years Bosch established itself as a strategic hub for innovation and production with a notable impact on Romania's technological landscape.

Emerson is an American industrial group. Emerson first entered the Romanian market in 2006, establishing a 12-hectare industrial campus within the Tetarom II industrial park in Cluj-Napoca. In 2021, it opened a new factory specializing in lighting fixtures and electrical panels for explosive atmospheres in the Urbano industrial park, located in Gilău commune. This new facility initially employs 110 people, with plans to expand its workforce. In 2024, Emerson has implemented the Kick-Off Your Career program for students in Cluj, which includes mentorship and training on key skills.⁵⁵ In 2020, the company employed 2,685 employees, according to data from the Ministry of Finance.⁵⁶

Technological parks

Liberty Technology Park Cluj is the first technological park in Romania, located in Cluj. The park is created for ICT and R&D companies to form one ecosystem. It offers predominantly office spaces with additional services. Siemens and IBM are among the park's residents.

Tetarom Scientific and Technological Parks is an industrial park for advanced technologies located in the municipality of Cluj-Napoca. It was constructed in 2003 and financed by the European Union (64,8%), the Romanian Government (21,6%), and the Cluj City Council (13,6%).⁵⁷ Nowadays, the park has expanded to four campuses. The park also has its business incubator designed to support start-up companies, attract students and young people who want to develop their business ideas.⁵⁸ Tetarom III is the most successful park project, which hosts companies like Bosch, De'longhi, Transylvania Bank, and others. Its estimated employment places is estimated at 7.500. and value of customer investments - over 600 million euros. Tetarom IV is currently on hold. Cluj Country has managed to secure its public position as the owner of the land at Tetarom I, and the owner of infrastructure at Tetarom I, II, and III.

Urbano Cluj Vest Industrial Park (UCV) is located in the Floreşti - Gilău area in Cluj County since 2020. The park offers facilities for logistics, warehousing and light production among others.⁵⁹

Cluster organizations and hubs

Cluj IT-Cluster is built based on the collaboration and communication between companies, universities and research institutes, authorities and the IT community. It offers access to facilities, collaborative environment with other players in the IT value chain and access to various services such as matchmaking events with potential partners or access to information on funding opportunities within EU and Romania. The cluster management also conducts lobbying activities with the purpose of shaping public policies and public financing opportunities to benefit the IT community.⁶⁰ Together with 4 consortium partners, Cluj IT Cluster, Technical University Cluj-Napoca, University Oradea and Chamber of Commerce and Industry Bistrita-Nasaud), Cluj IT-Cluster has founded **Cluj Digital Innovation Hub (DIG4Society)**.

Transylvania IT Cluster was founded in 2013. It works at the intersection between entrepreneurship, researchers, innovators, and public administration, pushing forward discussion and action around digital transformation and thus enhancing community development through digitization. The Cluster also participates in lobbying for the development of digital policy and other actions to benefit the IT community. Together with 4 other clusters covering Wood Manufacturing, Agrofood, Energy & Creative, the Industries sectors, Transylvania IT Cluster has founded Transylvania Digital Innovation Hub (TDIH).⁶¹

Cluj Hub - coworking space and startup incubator in the city center of Cluj-Napoca that stimulates IT community development.

Our interviews reveal that several associations have been formed as umbrella organizations to promote, support and represent interests of certain groups of entrepreneurs. For instance, **RO TSA (Romanian Tech Startups Association)** works for tech startups in Romania.

Educational helix

- Babeş-Bolyai University
- Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
- University of Medicine and Pharmacy 'Iuliu Hațieganu'
- University of Agricultural Science and Veterinary Medicine
- University of Art and Design in Cluj-Napoca
- The National Academy of Music 'Gheorghe Dima'
- Sapientia Hungarian University
- Informal School of IT
- University Bogdan Voda Cluj-Napoca
- 'Dimitrie Cantemir' Christian University

Private helix

- De'Longhi
- Bosch Automotive
- Emerson

Public helix

- Cluj-Napoca Municipality
- North-West Regional Development Agency

In-between helices organizations

- Center for Imagination and Civic Innovation (CIIC) (part of Cluj-Napoca Municipality)

Ecosystem Infrastructure

- Liberty Technology Park Cluj
- Tetarom Scientific and Technological Parks
- Urbano Cluj Vest Industrial Park (UCV)
- Cluj "Avram Iancu" International Airport
- Cluj Hub
- Transylvania IT Cluster
- Cluj IT-Cluster

Basque Country

The Spanish region has a comprehensive governance structure to govern the economic transition towards knowledge economy, which was established since the foundation of the independent Basque Country. Compared to the Dutch case—where a single large organization, Brainport Development, performs all the functions of supporting the innovation ecosystem—in the Basque Country, these functions are distributed across several specialized institutions that operate between the helices.

Government

Within the Basque Government, the **Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment Department** was particularly important for the transition. It was a crucial initiator of the SPRI, Basque Business Development Agency, the driving leader of the transition in the 1980th. The **Department of Labor and Employment** also takes an active role in collaborating with institutions on labor integration and skilling sectors.

Universities

Basque Country is home to 3 main universities and a number of vocational and educational training schools. The main universities are:

Private University of Deusto was founded by the Society of Jesus (Jesuits) in 1886. It was established with the aim of providing higher education rooted in Catholic values, with a strong focus on social responsibility, cooperation, and the development of the Basque region. It offers a wide range of undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral programs, with a focus on business, law, and social sciences and is recognized for its international partnerships, fostering collaboration between academia, industry, and global institutions.

Private University of Mondragon was founded in 1989 by the Mondragon Corporation, a cooperative organization in the Basque Country. It was established by a group of visionary individuals, including José María Arizmendiarieta, a Catholic priest and social entrepreneur, who played a pivotal role in promoting cooperative principles and the creation of a cooperative-based educational institution. The university was created to support the educational needs of the workers in the cooperative movement, with a focus on applied knowledge and community development. Nowadays the university offers programs with a focus on innovation, entrepreneurship, and sustainable development. The university is renowned for linking academic knowledge with practical experience, and its strong commitment to social entrepreneurship and regional development.

Public University of Basque Country (UPV/EHU), established in 1980, is the largest public university in the Basque Country, offering a broad range of academic programs across various fields, including sciences, humanities, and social sciences. It was founded with the goal of promoting higher education and research in the Basque Country while preserving and enhancing the Basque language and culture. The university plays a key role in regional economic development through its research initiatives, research centers, and collaborations with local industries and government institutions.

New types of organizations that emerge to support multi-helix collaboration

SPRI, Basque Business Development Agency, was founded in 1981 by the Department of Industry of the Basque Government (now restructured into the Department of Economic Development, Sustainability, and Environment). Referring to a study by Morisson & Doussineau, the agency was established to support the 'First Great Transformation' – a program set up to stimulate industrial restructuring to deal with the industrial crisis that resulted in large unemployment and regional decline.⁶² Since then the agency's mission has evolved from industrial restructuring towards driving competitiveness and innovations in the region. SPRI is fully dependent on the Basque government in its financial support.

Orkerstra, Basque Institute of Competitiveness, is public-private institute, founded in 2006, to study regional competitiveness in the country in order to foster wellbeing and regional development. Orkerstra was created as a result of collaboration between the University of Deusto, public administration and major firms in the Basque Country. According to a study by Gray (2022), initially the Basque government was the single funder of the institute, however today around 60 percent of institute's funding comes from "a mix of public and private stakeholders—the Basque government is its largest funder—while the remaining c.40 percent comes from competitive research grants and teaching activities."⁶³ The institute is organized around 5 core labs that conduct research and living labs, implement teaching and training programs, and organize dissemination activities such as workshops, seminars, and conferences. The labs are Public Policy and Institutions Lab, Enterprise Lab, Wellbeing Lab, Digital Economy Lab, and Energy Lab.⁶⁴

Innobasque, Basque Innovation Agency, initiated in 2007 by the Basque government to make Basque Country the leading region in innovations. It is a private, non-profit initiative that was supported through public and private funding, in order to allow for independence from the government and flexibility in terms of organization and activities. It focuses on driving innovations of broad scope, whether it is technological, organizational, social or business processes innovations.

We are private. That's very important because a lot of people think that we are public. We are a rare, strange, and living entity because we are private. [...] We are a private association, but you will see that most of the income comes from the government. However, the thing is that we have the word agency in our name. Literally, an agency is an executive arm of the government is the arm that makes policies come to reality. (Interview, Basque Country, 2024)

As Morisson & Doussineau write: "The organization identified and coordinated 1000 partners coming from the private sector (73%), universities and research centers (15%), and the public sector and the civil society (12%) to form working groups to identify weaknesses in the Basque innovation system regarding technological innovation, social innovation, internationalization, organizational innovation and entrepreneurship."⁶⁵

BRTA, the Basque Research and Technology Alliance, is an alliance of 17 research and technology organizations (RTOs). The RTOs are multidisciplinary, working in many fields of science and technology. Legally, BRTA is a consortium belonging to the public sector, supported by the Basque Government, SPRI and the Provincial Councils of Araba, Bizkaia and Gipuzkoa.⁶⁶

As an entity, the alliance was created only in 2019, but its member organizations have existed for some decades now, for example the School for Agriculture exists since 1978. The alliance has its roots in the 1980th; during that period, they were supporting industries "that had the ingredients to be competitive in the future but weren't quite there yet to upgrade them, so they would reconvert them in a way,"— explains one of our informants.

Similar to the other organizations, the mission of BRTA is to stimulate competitiveness and innovations. However, the focus in this case is done on three key areas, supporting the internationalization of RTOs, setting up a research agenda to address the most acute challenges in the region (in the area of smart industry, cleaner energy, personalized health and healthy food), and the technology transfer: *“We are, for instance, exchanging good practices for patents or we have made a campaign to reach small and medium-sized companies,”* – explains one of the representatives of BRTA in our interview.

Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, was founded in 2007 by the Basque Government to reinforce Basque science system. Their activities directed at promotion of scientific research, we well as attraction, recovery and retention of international researchers.⁶⁷ Ikerbasque develops and implements recruitment programs for researchers with different profiles.

Private companies

The private sector is divided in for-profit businesses and non-profit private companies, such as research or technological centers, whose aim is to perform research or knowledge/technology transfer. Basque Country has a strong business sector; however, the majority of the companies are small and medium-sized. That is why the cluster strategies are so strongly developed in the sector. The largest businesses in the region are:

Mondragon Corporation is the largest business group in the Basque Country and the tenth largest in Spain.⁶⁸ It employs more than 70.000 workers in total, with 30,660 being in Basque country.⁶⁹ Apart from being a corporation successful in four areas: finance, industry, retail, and knowledge, Mondragon is also a cooperative of workers. The companies’ values are rooted in principles of solidarity and participation. Its origins trace back to the vision of José María Arizmendiarieta, a Catholic priest who emphasized the importance of education and technical expertise for fostering social and economic transformation. Starting with the creation of a technical college in 1943 and the establishment of the first cooperative, the corporation expanded rapidly, supported by many other institutions like the local banks or welfare bodies. Now, the Mondragon Cooperative Group embodies a unique model of cooperative industrial and social development. Education and innovation are at the heart of the Mondragon Corporation’s success, serving as key drivers of its development. Its large knowledge and innovation network encompass Mondragon University, technology centers, and educational initiatives, which cements its position as a leader in cooperative and technological advancement.

Iberdrola is a multinational electric utility company headquartered in Bilbao. It employs approximately 40,000 people and serves 30 million customers globally. Recognized as the largest producer of wind power, Iberdrola is also the world’s second-largest electricity utility by market capitalization.⁷⁰

BBVA is a multinational financial services company headquartered in Bilbao. It is one of the largest financial institutions globally. Established in 1857 as Banco de Bilbao, BBVA operates across Spain, Portugal, Mexico, South America, Turkey, Italy, and Romania, serving over 71 million customers in more than 30 countries as of 2023. It is Spain’s second-largest bank by assets, totaling approximately €775 billion.⁷¹

Eroski is a supermarket chain originating from the Basque Country. It operates nearly 1,000 stores across Spain and functions as a worker-consumer hybrid cooperative within the Mondragón Corporation. It was founded in 1969 as a cooperative between ten supermarkets in Biscay and Gipuzkoa.⁷²

Technological parks and clusters

Basque Country Technology Park is a large network, which encompasses nice campuses across the Basque region. The network includes campuses in Araba, Bizkaia, and Gipuzkoa, each hosting various companies and research centers. One of the campuses is **Biscay Science and Technology Park**, which was established in 1985 and now stands as a pioneering and successful model in Spain.⁷³

Apart from the newly created organizations founded for collaboration in-between helices, many existing organizations have been united into **networks** without forming a separate institution. These networks become important bodies for exchanging knowledge and expertise. Moreover, they represent their communities locally and abroad. For example, one such network is **SARETEK**, a Basque Network of Science, Technology and Innovation. Another, the **Basque Technology Network**, was founded in 1997 by the Basque Government by publishing Decree 96/1997, which established the relations of collaboration and coordination with the technological research entities in the region and determined the criteria and functions of the participating entities.⁷⁴

Private organizations organize themselves into industrial sectors, which have set up **sectorial organizations** to promote collaborations among companies within sector, as well as between them and external companies. The sectorial clusters in Basque Country have been founded within several industries: aeronautics and Space; automotive; ICTs and Knowledge; energy; food; bio-health; construction; maritime industry; Advanced Manufacturing Technologies; environmental industries; paper; transport, mobility and logistics, and others.⁷⁵ Each of these clusters is led by a cluster association – a leading organization within the cluster.

Educational helix

- University of Deusto
- University of Mondragon
- University of Basque Country (UPV/EHU)

Private helix

- Mondragon Corporation
- Iberdrola
- BBVA
- Eroski

Public helix

- Basque Government

In-between helices organizations

- SPRI
- Orkestra
- Innobasque
- BRTA
- Ikerbasque

Ecosystem Infrastructure

- Basque Country Technology Park

Exploring the role of each helix in governing innovations

In this section, we explore the role of each helix in the multi-helix governance model, with particular attention to the role of the public sector—governments and educational institutions. The knowledge economy requires the transformation of their structures and roles, and our aim is to document this transformation. We approach this from a comparative perspective. First, we examine the role of government in each of the three regions, highlighting both similarities and differences. Next, we focus on the role of educational institutions. As our focus is not on serving knowledge creation for the private sector, we do not delve extensively into this nexus. Regarding the civil society sector, we actively attempted to study its role in the economic transition. However, the data from all three regions reveal its very limited involvement. We consider this outcome one of the key findings of our research.

The role of government

In this section, we examine the role of government in three transition regions, summarized in Table 2 below. Our case studies reveal that after industrial decline and significant unemployment, regional governments played a pivotal role in driving transitions and fostering collaboration with industry and education sectors. While the regions representing the South, North, and Eastern Europe exhibited distinct differences in government's roles, several commonalities emerged.

The most notable commonality lies in the approach taken by all three regional governments to transition from supporting an industrial economy to fostering an innovation- or digital-driven economy. This transformation has introduced new governmental roles:

1. Government as public venture capitalist

Governments have taken on the role of venture capitalists by creating independent executive agencies that act like private organizations to implement public policies, strategies, and programs. Among the three regions, the Brainport government is the most active in realizing this role through its executive agency – Brainport Development. Consolidating public funding from the 21 municipalities, as well as private and academic funds, Brainport government invests annually between 8 and 15 million in stimulating innovations, facilitating startups, developing physical and intellectual infrastructure, as well as aggressively attracting international talents.

In Cluj, the government's financial and labor capacities are limited to act as a venture capitalist. The government has not been able to set up a formal executive agency. The government has invested large public resources in the development of physical infrastructure for clusters where large international companies are located, but limited resources have been invested in the development of IT ecosystem, for instance, talent attraction, legal base development. The interviews reveal that the startup community are consolidating their own resources to develop technological hubs and clusters, necessary for the IT industry.

While the government in the Basque Country also stimulates the promotion of intellectual and startup infrastructure, as well as physical infrastructure, it is more restricted in attracting international talents due to the region's strong local identity and local language.

2. Government as developer of 'soft' infrastructure for knowledge and innovation ecosystem

This role of government involves assembling non-tangible or 'soft' elements required for the ecosystem, such as a) regulations, and b) talents or knowledge.

a) Designing policies, laws, and regulations. The key legal frameworks necessary for an innovation ecosystem include:

- A legal framework **to protect and enforce intellectual property (IP) rights**. The primary forms of intellectual property protection are patents, copyrights, trademarks, and trade secrets.
- A legal framework **to facilitate cluster infrastructure**, enabling startups and SMEs to innovate and scale their businesses.

Basque Country has regional laws and regulations established since the foundation of the autonomous region. These regulations promote knowledge transfer, protect intellectual property, and stimulate patent creation and cluster development. The Dutch system also provides comprehensive policies for cluster development, knowledge transfer, IP protection, and patent creation, but these are implemented at the national level. In contrast, as later discussed in Chapter 4.2, Cluj County in Romania lacks key regulations in this sphere, at both the national and regional levels.

b) Attracting and retaining talent and knowledge to facilitate labor market development. A key government responsibility is ensuring a well-supplied labor market by attracting talent to the region and providing training and re-skilling opportunities necessary for ecosystem growth.

Different instruments can be employed to achieve this. For example, in Southeast North Brabant, a comprehensive strategy addresses both talent attraction and retention by creating favorable conditions for expats and their families. This includes tax benefits, expat services such as language courses and community building, visa assistance, career support for expat spouses, and the provision of physical infrastructure such as international schools and housing.⁷⁶ In Basque Country, talent attraction is mainly established via a specialized agency, the Basque Foundation for Science, whose activities aim to attracting and retaining international researchers. However, compared to the Brainport government, the Basque government is taking a less proactive approach to attracting external talents to the region. Instead, Basque government aims to improve conditions for local labor force. This strategy was selected in light of the aging population in the region. A project of Gizatea, a local NGO for Social Integration Companies supported by the Basque Employment Service of the Basque Government aims at improving conditions for employment for unemployed people in situation of exclusion, such as international migrants and refugees⁷⁷. The project, which is still in its conceptual stage, aims to obtain international diplomas and offer relevant skill training for those groups of people. Cluj County has been relying on a public branding strategy or tax incentives to attract international and domestic workers (see more on page 62). However, their mechanisms to retain talents are limited.

3. Government as developer of physical infrastructure to accommodate technological advancements and ecosystem growth

This role includes:

- Constructing housing to support an expanding workforce.
- Establishing educational institutions, such as international schools, to cater to the needs of a global talent pool.
- Regulating land policies to align with the region’s economic demands and support industry clusters.

4. In Cluj County, one key role of public governance, particularly the mayor and their administration, is **to lend credibility to private companies in grant applications**. This collaborative approach helps secure external funding and fosters trust at an international level. As one business manager in the tech industry explained: “I’m apolitical, I do not have to take part [in politics], but the mayor represents the administration, and each time we go together, we are very credible at the international level”. (Interview, Cluj, 2023). This role is explained by the weak position of government in the development of ecosystem due to low financial and human resources. Attracting external grants, particularly through the European Economic Area (EEA), Norwegian programs, and other European funding initiatives, is critical for driving innovation and supporting social projects there.

Conclusion. Navigating the tension between public investment and private gain: governance

challenges in innovation ecosystems and instruments to address them.

Addressing one of the research questions we posed—how the roles of universities, industry, and government can be balanced, and what public governance instruments can help avoid asymmetry that hinders this balance—we can derive several lessons from the three regions.

First, in the example of Brainport government, it takes a particularly active role in supporting innovation. There, the government tries to act as an entrepreneurial actor, albeit constrained by its public mandate. A strategic adviser to the local government explained: “They [local government] don’t finance innovations directly; they finance programs that develop innovation.” While the government aims to drive innovation and economic growth, it uses public instruments to assist private capital in realizing their interests. As our findings suggest, the Brainport government

lacks public instruments to constrain private capital and to value capture that can be used for the public good. The quote below by the representative of the Eindhoven municipality highlights the weak position of government in gaining value from the developed ecosystem:

“In the most ideal situation, we want the ownership [of the land and building of a technological cluster] and we want public involvement because these are real assets like say, the High-Tech campus, the Brainport Industries Campus, but also the Automotive Campus in Helmand, the TU/e Campus in the city center... like we called ‘our jewels’, where are we, the Brainport region, so really our assets, where we can make the future. And you want to keep them, and you want to have public involvement, so you can do the steering when necessary. But that’s a complicated question because it’s connected to ‘Do you have ground position? Do you have influence?’ We’re not a shareholder, for example.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

This tension between public investment and private gain is an ongoing challenge in the governance of innovation ecosystems. The government is trying to address it by using an instrument of Erfpacht [in Dutch for ground lease], which presents very limited possibilities in securing government’s position.

GOOD PRACTICE

Governance instrument – Erfpacht [Ground lease]

Ground lease is the right to use land owned by the Dutch municipality. The municipality (or the lessor) charges a fee for this, and the leaseholders (individual or commercial enterprises) are bound by conditions. These conditions are stated in the deed drawn up by the notary when the leaseholder purchases the leasehold right. Within these conditions, the leaseholder has rights and obligations of the owner. The leaseholder pays an annual fee for using the land, or sometimes can buy the land in perpetuity.

Leasehold rules offer municipalities the possibility to impose boundary conditions on the use of land. For instance, for industrial estates, a leasehold structure makes it easier to restructure when it becomes obsolete, because in the event of vacancy and demolition, only the market value of the built object plays a role and not the possible value of the land. From the perspective of the municipality, a leasehold system ensures stable cash flows instead of one-off payment.

Even though in case of the Brainport the leasehold does not allow the municipalities to act as an equal stakeholder in the development of the Brainport Industries Campus or value the capture, it allows to have a little bit more influence.

*- And how do you mean that the leasehold rule will help the municipality to get more influence?
- Because then we are the owner of the ground. So, we have something more to say in it, [...] The ideal situation is that we are the shareholder, because then you have some influence as a municipality on the ecosystem and the campus itself. So not the building and the individual tenants but the ecosystem and the campus are really important. And there you want to keep it and you want to help it, and you want to make it better. And I think there is a role for the municipality. And if have a shareholder or something... Then you have more to tell. It’s that simple. Of course, you have the regular procedures where the municipalities are involved, like from zoning plan and vergunning [Dutch] - when you need permission to build something or so... there are of course regular instruments but that we want something more in this development.”*

In this respect, the Basque government’s policy priorities (described in Chapter 4, page 64) can serve as the best practice that directs economic growth to serve the societal aims. The priorities steer the economic development in the direction of social challenges. This is done by offering public funding for specific areas, such as green economy or aging population.

Role	SOUTHEAST NORTH BRABANT	CLUJ COUNTY	BASQUE COUNTRY
1. Act as a public venture capitalist	●	●	●
2. Developing 'soft' infrastructure for knowledge and innovation ecosystem	●	●	●
a) Legal base to protect and enforce intellectual property (IP) right and facilitate cluster infrastructure	●	●	●
b) Facilitating labor market development and attracting talent	●○	●	●○
3. Developing physical infrastructure for knowledge and innovation ecosystem	●	●	●
4. Mayor's endorsement helps private companies and clusters win grant calls at the EEA/EU level (under condition of limited resources and necessity to attract EU funding)		●	

○ Focus on attracting, but also talents available locally

Table 2. Summary of the role of government in three transition regions.

The role of educational institutions

In this section, we explore the evolving role of educational institutions in the transition to a knowledge economy. First, we trace the evolution of the university's role, which has expanded beyond its third mission of addressing societal challenges. Second, we apply this transformation to our case studies, taking a comparative approach. The academic systems in the three regions provide varying conditions for university participation in knowledge transfer. From our experience across these cases, we have observed that, in the context of the knowledge economy, the university's role has further evolved into an entrepreneurial entity. Universities capitalize on knowledge, transforming research groups into private research centers capable of launching spin-offs and engaging in the global capital market.

In the context of knowledge-based economy, universities are increasingly recognized not only as institutions for education and research but also as key drivers of societal and economic development. This shift has given rise to the concept of the "third mission" of universities. The third mission emphasizes their active engagement in fostering innovation, contributing to regional and national development, and addressing complex societal challenges.⁷⁸ By collaborating with governments, industries, and civil society, universities broaden their focus from merely generating knowledge to applying it in ways that enhance competitiveness, sustainability, and social equity. This transformation requires a new organizational structure within universities that facilitates not only the creation of knowledge but also its valorization and capitalization. Valorization refers to the practical utilization of scientific knowledge, while capitalization – to creating capital on it. University structure changes to accommodate these two functions to include independent research institutes, laboratories, and centers, which enable scientific and research teams to operate as private entities, thereby competing within the private sector. Public universities, thus, become organizations that provide education and research in the fields that do not allow capitalization of knowledge.

The key role of universities in the knowledge economy includes: 1) provision of talent and human resources suited for the development of the knowledge economy, 2) valorization of knowledge to support innovation, and 3) capitalization of knowledge.

1. Provision of talents and human resources for the knowledge economy

This first function aligns with what Bogers and Steinbuch (2023) describe as the 'Classical University'⁷⁹, whose primary role was to provide education and disseminate knowledge to individuals in society. Traditionally, education has been a means to foster critical thinking, intellectual curiosity, and personal growth, all of which contribute broadly to societal development. However, within the framework of the knowledge economy, this educational function has shifted. The focus is now on providing skills and knowledge specifically tailored to drive entrepreneurship, technological advancements, and support innovations. As a result, there has been a pronounced prioritization of technical and natural sciences, which are often viewed as the engines of economic growth. In contrast, the value of the humanities and social sciences has become less visible, despite their crucial role in addressing the ethical, social, and cultural dimensions of innovation.⁸⁰

The Dutch education system scores the highest among the three countries studied in both international outlook and quality, as per The Times Higher Education World University Rankings 2024.⁸¹ However, the current political climate poses significant challenges to this high standing. The recently elected right-wing coalition government has announced plans to cut €1 billion from the higher education and science budget—almost 10% of the total educational budget. This includes a €300 million reduction in international education funding and limits on foreign student enrollment through the proposed Balanced Internationalization Bill.⁸² This policy introduces considerable uncertainty for all Dutch universities. These governmental changes may threaten the Netherlands' global engagement in science and education, diminishing the international appeal of Dutch universities. Such a trajectory could have negative consequences for the country's innovation and knowledge-driven

economy. The University of the Basque Country ranks among 601-800th position in the World University Ranking, while Babeş-Bolyai University ranks among 1001-1200th position.

In the context of provision of human resources in the knowledge economy, two key trends can be observed:

1) The importance of secondary vocational education

In the knowledge economy, it has become essential to train individuals who not only generate knowledge, but also possess applied skills to develop technologies. In Brainport region, universities of applied sciences (or institutions of secondary vocational education), such as Summa College, have become crucial actors in the innovation ecosystem. The following quote from an interview with a public policy adviser highlights this point:

What's forgotten a lot is that if it's technology, it's always high end. It's always the well-educated. [In fact] The most people we are searching for (but also working with) are people who are making things - MBO level [secondary vocational education in Dutch system]. So, you see companies like ASML, these are the whiz kids, they are very important. But they can't make a product if people with MBO level can't make the product itself - fabricate it." (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

According to our informants, the education system at Romania universities (including Cluj) is not oriented on applied skills for the digital economy, except at the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca:

"I feel that universities have a hard time connecting with the whole innovation environment. Some are better connected, like my university [Babeş-Bolyai University], but it mostly has to do with the fact that it's a big university with a lot of experience in research and there is a very easy transition from research to innovation, which is very close. Or the technical universities are connected with the IT environment. Other universities are very passive, and a lot of the entrepreneurial courses or universities are old school, and not oriented towards a direct result." (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

In the Basque Country, while our interview data on this matter is limited, publicly available information confirms that vocational training is integrated into the strategy for ecosystem development.

2) The Importance of collaboration and spatial proximity between schools and industries

The spatial proximity of schools and industries has become crucial for the efficiency of the innovation ecosystem, particularly in sectors with high complexity, such as semiconductors. In Brainport, industries and schools engage in mutually beneficial partnerships: industries provide expensive machinery that schools cannot afford, while schools offer the relevant skills to students, enhancing their employability. Innovation clusters and campuses facilitate this necessary proximity. The following quote from an interview with a public policy adviser further illustrates this point:

"The Summa [College] is at the Brainport Industries Campus. They are very closely connected to the companies. Because the companies are on that Brainport Industries Campus... They work with machines very high end, and they have to. And they want people of Summa who can work with the machines. And Summa can't afford to buy these machines, [it is] too expensive. They are very pricey. So, people at Summa work at the companies, so they are trained on the job. [...] So, what is needed at the moment. The skills... The skills you need. That is, tomorrow, different than today. So yeah, it has to be on the job. It has to be... education has to be in the company." (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

In Cluj, the interviews reveal that one of the main challenges of the Romanian academic system is to find qualified people and stimulate them to engage in activities beyond education, such as collaborations with industrial partners.

(1) "There are two things. One, you need to find them [qualified people]. But then you need to clear the space for them to do this. [...] They would be pushed to teaching. They will not

be allowed to play with the students on different projects. They might be paid for that, but they need to teach. So, it's very difficult for the university to say: look you should move to half teaching position and leave room for developing students' projects. It could be solved but it's not yet considered a priority." (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

(2) "[There are] no actual incentives in place, although there are strategies and plans in place for this". (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

2. Valorization of knowledge or knowledge transfer

Valorization refers to the practical application of scientific knowledge. During the Industrial Revolution, universities underwent a transformation into what Bogers and Steinbuch (2023) describe as the research university.⁸³ This shift was driven by the growing demand for scientific knowledge to support industrial progress and societal development. A key aspect of the university's evolving mission became knowledge transfer — the process of translating academic research and expertise into practical applications that benefit society. This knowledge transfer often occurs through partnerships with industry, collaborations with government, and technology transfer via patents and licensing. In doing so, universities play a crucial role in innovation ecosystems, bridging the gap between theoretical insights and real-world solutions.

Regarding the organizational structure, universities focused more on the systematic creation of new knowledge through research. They established specialized laboratories that became central hubs for experimentation, innovation, and scientific breakthroughs. Those labs were integral parts of university departments. For example, in the University of Basque Country, the research groups that produce knowledge transfer have been separated from the university structure into independent technological and research centers that are funded by public and private sources.⁸⁴ The quote below by a university representative specializing in knowledge transfer highlights the challenge for the university:

"Even if we make a lot of transfer and we have excellent groups, you know that we have the technological centers. Here, there are quite a lot of centers that are public funded that have personnel from the university. People from the university are also linked to the centers. For example, we have the mathematics center or the materials center and it's the same persons that is at the university and at the center. This is something that the Basque government, the industry part has pushed for, is that the university is for teaching and the research is made in the centers. That is something that is not good for the university because it's decapitalized. It's the same person, but when they do research, they sign with another [affiliation]. In that sense we have the education part, and we have the industry part." (Interview, Basque Country, 2024)

Effective knowledge transfer relies heavily on the role of the public government to create governance structures that foster collaboration while safeguarding academic integrity. However, issues of ownership, intellectual property rights, and equitable benefit-sharing remain contentious. This evolving role of universities calls for an expansion of mechanisms outlined in the previous chapter — such as intellectual property (IP) rights and cluster infrastructure — as well as the promotion of open science and participatory research. These approaches democratize access to knowledge and empower broader societal engagement in innovation processes.

Lastly, our interviews emphasize the importance of the material dimension in knowledge transfer. Funding research and knowledge production alone, without the necessary infrastructure to apply this knowledge in ways that create societal value, is insufficient. By infrastructure, we mean campuses, clusters, and parks.

In North Brabant, as in the Basque Country, there is an extensive policy and strategic framework at both the national level and within universities. In 2005, the Dutch government recognized valorization as a third core priority for universities.⁸⁵ In 2023, Dutch universities introduced an

innovative set of regulations known as the ‘deal terms’, which establish transparent conditions for the rapid growth of university spin-offs.⁸⁶ Notably, these deal terms were not developed by the government but by a collaborative working group comprising universities, investors, and entrepreneurs. The primary goal of the deal terms is to streamline the negotiation process between universities and emerging SMEs, thereby enhancing opportunities for growth and success.

“The deal terms set out the fees and agreements around intellectual property rights. They are envisaged for situations in which a researcher terminates their employment and wants to start up a company on the basis of intellectual property deriving from the university’s activities.”⁸⁷

In Cluj, despite being home to the largest concentration of universities in Romania, interviews reveal that the academic system provides precarious conditions that significantly hinder opportunities for knowledge transfer. Even the largest university lacks a formal strategy for knowledge and technology transfer, as well as established procedures for managing intellectual property.

(1) “The university doesn’t have a strategy on this [collaborations with industry]. It is very much opportunity based: if there is funding, or if there any an interest, where they [students] can connect, get some funding, it’s going to become interesting. [...] The universities are beginning to use opportunities that come from different institutions, through different programs. It’s far from what is happening in Western Europe, but it’s significantly better compared to what it was 3,4,5 years ago.” (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

(2) “Universities in Romania do not have structured procedures on intellectual property and technology transfer - for example a researcher can have a patent that the university supports with paying the fees while never trying to monetize it (because it helps their career). Plus, at the same time a researcher could take the result of a project funded by the university into a private firm and monetize it without the university as a partner or beneficiary and the universities do not care. [...] Although numerous universities have regulations on their websites, in practice they are not concerned with tech transfer (partly because of little to no original research production).” (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

One of the key strengths of the Basque Country’s approach to developing knowledge economy lies in the government’s strong emphasis on strategic and policy foundations. The region has implemented comprehensive policies aimed at enhancing the quality of Basque education, promoting its internationalization, and strengthening its connection to society and business. The first important strategic document is the “2020 Internationalization Framework Strategy”⁸⁸, initially approved by Basque government in 2014 and later updated in 2025.⁸⁹ This strategy is an important step in attracting international talents and training high-quality professions locally.

The second crucial strategic document is the ‘Framework Strategy Universities + Euskadi Basque Country 2030’. This strategy aligns closely with the strategy of Basque University System Plan 2023-2026,⁹⁰ sharing internationalization as its primary focus. Together, these strategies play a vital role in fostering university-business-society cooperation. Additionally, universities in the Basque Country align their knowledge transfer strategies with those of the government, ensuring coherence and collaboration.

Another significant strength of the Basque Country’s approach is the establishment of the 4gune Engineering, Science, and Technology Cluster. This specialized cluster focuses on strengthening university-business cooperation in the region and promoting collaborative models in the field of Smart Industry. The creation of such a cluster provides fertile ground for knowledge transfer, facilitates training opportunities for students and university staff, and strengthens relationships between the university system, the business sector, and broader society.⁹¹

Based on these points, in Cluj, the knowledge transfer at universities is weaker than in Basque Country and Southeast North Brabant (see Table 3).

GOOD PRACTICE

How public government stimulated knowledge transfer at Eindhoven University of Technology and supported unemployed workers at bankrupted DAF

In one of our interviews, we have heard an interesting story about the collaboration between the unemployed DAF workers and scientists of Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e). This collaboration, motivated by central government through knowledge workers arrangement significantly strengthened knowledge transfer at TU/e and provided support for the unemployed DAF knowledge workers.

[...] I still remember that DAF told me that in one week they lost 60% of their order intake. So, they were really in bad weather, like many other companies in this region... NXP, Phillips... [...] And then we invented it [a knowledge workers arrangement], and that that idea came from our region, the knowledge workers arrangement- the kenniswerkersregeling [in Dutch]. And the idea was instead of having people pushed into the unemployment and the central government paying for the unemployment salaries, we asked the government: OK, please pay that same amount of money to the companies. And in return, the companies keep the people within their organization. It was sort of free money for companies. In order to be allowed to do that, the companies had to take those knowledge workers, for which they got the money... They had to set them into separate knowledge workers projects. Mainly located at knowledge institutes.

So, in 2009 and 2010, I had 15 people from DAF, who were in my lab here. And the salaries of those 15 people were being paid from the government, central government to DAF, and the people were still employed by DAF, but they were located in my lab, as part of the knowledge workers arrangement. And those people they were very interesting for the [research] group because those were 15 people with, on average 10 years of experience with DAF. So, I got in my lab from one day to another, 150 years of experience of industry, in my lab. And for those DAF people, it was so nice to be able to read the paper again in the library without pressure of time. And for my researchers in powertrain development for cars and trucks, they were really happy that they had 150 years of experience next door on the same hallway. So, in those one and a half years, we developed - so my scientists and those 15 people from DAF - we developed the first hybrid truck. So, truck with an electrical motor, in addition to the gasoline motor. And after one and half years, those people went back and with them also the idea for this hybrid truck and it became the first hybrid truck of DAF.

So, with that in mind, we in fact accelerated innovation by taking people from the industry, putting them in academia for a limited amount of time and to also influencing our academic people by this practical knowledge and really focusing like a student team focused on an outcome to develop something. And that taught me really to accelerate innovation by opening the doors of the university and getting people from outside in. So those things have been crucial and instrumental for this region, to all the time be creative in those periods where it was difficult to see how we can help, as university, how can we help the industry, and vice versa. If it’s difficult to get funding, how the industry can help us, et cetera. That that is the way... And those ideas are created here basically, the knowledge workers, it was for all of the Netherlands, but we invented it.

3. Capitalization of knowledge.

In the late 20th century, universities evolved into what is often called the entrepreneurial university. This shift marked a significant departure from their traditional roles in education and research, as universities began to position themselves as key economic actors. The emergence of the triple-helix model, which underscores dynamic interactions between universities, industry, and government, reflects this transformation. Entrepreneurial universities took on roles beyond knowledge dissemination and production, focusing on the commercialization of research outputs, fostering start-ups and spinoffs.⁹²

This change redefined the role of universities, embedding them more directly into the economic fabric. It allowed them to act as catalysts for regional economic development and technological advancement. However, this shift has sparked debates about the consequences of such market-oriented engagement. Critics argue that prioritizing economic objectives could undermine the core educational and research missions of universities, potentially creating tensions between academic freedom and commercial interests.⁹³

Nonetheless, some industry representatives believe that universities are not well-equipped to produce market-driven innovations because they lack a clear understanding of market needs.

“The universities are very good at creating talent, providing knowledge, and making research projects but, at least currently, they are not so well prepared to introduce innovation on the market. While the companies are looking at the market needs, they have a completely different approach to innovations. [...] We are having also the universities along, also the public administration, but doing their role, not trying to do what the company should do.” (Interview, Cluj, 2023).

To encourage research production and its practical application, universities have established various incentives for their employees. In Brainport region, alongside the national-level deal terms, universities implement their own specific regulations regarding patents and inventions. For example, the Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) has outlined detailed rules covering aspects such as collaboration, compensation structures, copyright ownership, and confidentiality.

An intriguing comparison can be made with a university in the Basque Country, where inventors can receive up to 60% of the profits generated from their inventions. At TU/e, however, the surplus of cash revenues directly linked to the exploitation of a patent is distributed according to the ‘33 1/3 % rule’, which ensures a balanced distribution of revenues, incentivizing individual researchers while supporting collective research efforts and the broader institutional framework.⁹⁴ Under this system:

- 33 1/3 % is allocated to the inventor(s). If multiple inventors are involved, this portion is divided equally among them.
- 33 1/3 % is directed to the inventor’s capacity group, department, management unit, or research institute to fund new research activities.
- 33 1/3 % is contributed to the patent fund of TU/e’s service structure.

In the Basque Country, universities employ various strategies to encourage their employees to engage in research and knowledge transfer. For example, a knowledge transfer specialist at a public university highlighted several key incentives during an interview:

- Financial Incentives: Monetary rewards are provided to researchers who actively participate in knowledge transfer activities.
- Reduction of Teaching Hours: Faculty members involved in research and knowledge transfer may benefit from reduced teaching responsibilities. This approach allows them to dedicate more time to research and innovation.

The practice of reducing teaching hours is particularly noteworthy. It could serve as a valuable model for Romanian universities, where the academic focus is heavily centered on teaching, leaving little room for flexibility or opportunities to engage in research and knowledge transfer activities.

(1) “[...] The university is also more and more promoting that [knowledge transfer]. For example, when the university makes a contract with an enterprise, private enterprise, the part of the contract goes to the research group and the other part goes to the professors that are developing the work. They can save that money for their laboratories and so on, or also, part of that money, they can have for them. You know, in the salaries. I think that is not common in other countries, but here, if the contract is made with a private enterprise, part of that income goes directly to that person. This is quite a very interesting incentive. The same thing happens with the licenses. If you license a patent also, 60 percent of the income of the university goes to inventors.” (Interview, Basque Country, 2024).

In regard to this, one constraint for the employees of the university to create startups and spinoffs is the Spanish law that restricts the share of the spinoff that the inventors are allowed to own. As a specialist from the university explains in the quote below this restriction de-incentivizes inventors:

*“Interviewee: In that sense we have a problem in this university is that, when a professor wants to create a spinoff, our regulation says that they cannot have more than 10 percent of the company. If the university doesn’t participate in that company (and our university never participates in the economic, I mean, in the spinoffs). That’s a barrier because, this morning I was talking to a professor saying, like 15 years ago I gave rise to an engineering company. I only had the 10 percent. Now it’s a big company and I didn’t have any money, you know. I would foster another two, but what for? This is something that we have to... There is a legal form now that we should have to enable that the professors that are pushing for these new companies can really participate in the capital.
Interviewer: Is it a regulation from the university or is it from the Basque government?
Interviewee: It’s from the Spanish law.”*
(Interview, Basque Country, 2024)

Role	NORTH BRABANT PROVINCE	CLUJ COUNTY	BASQUE COUNTRY
1. Provision of talents and human resources	●	●	●
2. Valorization of knowledge for the development of innovations	●	●	●
3. Capitalization of knowledge	●	●	●

Table 3. Summary of the role of educational institutions in three transition regions.

The role of private actors in transition regions

Private actors are integral to the transition to a digital and innovation-driven economy, driving innovation, production, investment, and job creation. Although our study did not explicitly focus on the private sector, we were able to derive relevant insights that highlight its role in this transformation.

1. Innovation and R&D

Private companies, particularly in the tech sector, invest in research and development to create new digital products and services. They lead innovation by developing emerging technologies like artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things (IoT), which are at the core of the digital economy.

2. Job Creation and Skill Development

As private companies develop new technologies and business models, they create jobs and facilitate skills development by offering training programs to help workers adapt to new technologies and stay competitive in the digital economy.

3. Financing and Investment

Private investors, including venture capitalists, angel investors, and large corporations, provide funding to startups and SMEs that are working on groundbreaking digital innovations. This helps fuel entrepreneurship and accelerates the growth of new business ideas that drive digital transformation.

In large companies with an external shareholder structure, the influence of external shareholders presents a significant challenge in decision-making processes, particularly when their interests diverge from the long-term needs of the region or local environment. External shareholders, driven primarily by profit motives, may prioritize short-term gains over sustainable practices or regional development, potentially undermining efforts to support local communities, promote environmental sustainability, or foster long-term economic resilience. This dynamic can lead to decisions that benefit shareholders at the expense of broader social and environmental objectives, thus posing risks to the integrity of local governance and the well-being of the region.

The role of civil society in transition regions

Despite our efforts to explore the role and participation of civil society in the triple-helix network, our findings highlight its limited influence in decision-making and its challenges in integrating into the network. Key obstacles include the high complexity and public inaccessibility of emerging technologies and innovations, the heterogeneity of civil society organizations, and difficulties in effectively representing the sector. Additionally, we identified the lack of experience and capacity among civil society actors in engaging with public policymaking processes. In both Cluj and Brainport, interviewees emphasized the need to strengthen civil society by fostering greater cohesion, enabling it to formulate common interests, and ensuring it can represent the sector on equal footing with the private and government sectors.

Besides, we found out that in Cluj the collaboration between civil society and private companies takes a form of mentorship, as illustrated in the following quotes by the NGO founder in Cluj:

"The CEO [Name] of this IT company, was one of the mentors. In the program, we should have like three sessions. After the three sessions, [Name] told me, "Look, I'm here whenever you need me. I want to work because I truly believe in what you do in there and let's do things together.[...] He's also offering us sponsorships. Also is a person who always connects us with people from City Hall, for example. I realized [Name] crediting us as experts was very important because he's a big player, in Cluj and has good connections with City Hall. [...] They are offering their meeting rooms. It's something that helps us because we don't have to pay for a meeting room, this kind of stuff." (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

Currently, Brainport is working on expanding its model beyond the triple helix by incorporating civil society as the fourth helix. The project aimed at developing the social agenda for Brainport is called 'Brainport voor Elkaar' (Dutch for 'Brainport for Each Other'). The program has been in development for over a year and remains in its early stages. It currently has four main pillars:

- 1) Facilitation of social innovations by supporting societal grassroots movements and NGO through matchmaking between entrepreneurs, companies, and (capital) funds that want to make a social contribution with charities and social initiatives that need money or materials.⁹⁵
- 2) Financial Fit: to prevent financial debts among the employees.
- 3) Language Fit: helping employees with low literacy levels strengthen their digital skills, language, and numeracy, among others.
- 4) Connecting different societal groups together through facilitation of corporate volunteering where employees of corporations volunteer with their labor, expertise and resources at social organizations.

The initiatives represent a significant step towards expanding beyond the triple helix model. However, it is important to note that most of the developed programs are implemented through large employers, such as ASML, with a primary focus on benefiting their own employees. While this offers support, it primarily benefits corporations themselves and fails to reach broader civil society beyond the network.

To conclude, key policy challenges in regard to the inclusion of civil society in triple-helix structure concern the following questions: Who can represent civil society to participate as a helix alongside the private sector, government, and academia? How can dispersed civil society groups collaborate to formulate a unified agenda for the civil society helix?

A potential 'best practice' to stimulate civil society unity and collective action can be drawn from the example of Latvia's umbrella organization for NGOs, The Civic Alliance - Latvia. Brainport could consider allocating funding to incentivize civil society organizations to collaborate, form a community, and potentially establish an umbrella organization to represent the sector more effectively.

GOOD PRACTICE

Umbrella Organization to Unite Civil Society

The Civic Alliance - Latvia (CAL) is the largest umbrella organization that advocates for non-governmental sector (NGO) interests. CAL aim is to strengthen civil society in Latvia, support the common interests of NGOs and create a favorable environment for their activities. The Civic Alliance- Latvia unites more than 130 members, making up a total of approximately 70,000 individuals or 70% of all persons involved in NGOs in Latvia and 27,500 individuals abroad or 11% of the Latvian diaspora.

Website: <https://nvo.lv/en/>

It was created to establish an organization capable of engaging with the government and public administration as an equal partner.

The primary aim of CAL is to enhance the legal and financial frameworks for NGOs and build their capacity for effective advocacy. CAL represents the interests of the NGO sector by lobbying, addressing challenges, promoting NGO participation in decision-making processes, and collaborating with public authorities. Additionally, CAL provides its members with information on topics such as EU policies, legislation, funding opportunities, education, motivation, and engagement, while also undertaking research initiatives.

Sources: Civic Alliance Latvia. (n.d.). About CAL. Available from: https://nvo.lv/en/content/about_cal (Accessed on December 12, 2024); Huber, S. (2011). Citizens Participation in Latvia: Still a Long Road to go? Universitätsverlag Potsdam. Available from: <https://d-nb.info/1218391057/34> (Accessed on December 12, 2024).

4. MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNANCE IN TRANSITION REGIONS

In this section, we examine governance across multiple levels: What roles do supranational, national, regional, and local governments play in governing economic transitions? Are these levels equally present in the three regions we study? And how are the different levels leveraged to stimulate economic transitions toward innovation?

The concept of multi-level governance has become central to governance and policy discussions. According to this framework, governance is territorially structured across different levels—local, regional, national, and supranational—with each level performing distinct functions. For example, in climate policy, supranational agreements like the Paris Agreement set overarching frameworks for coordinated climate action across borders. National governments then align their policies to meet these goals, such as implementing carbon taxes to drive national climate action. At the regional level, multiple municipalities may collaborate to develop policies that guide economic transitions away from polluting industries. Finally, local governments often focus on direct engagement with residents, implementing neighborhood-level measures such as promoting home insulation to reduce energy consumption.

While widely adopted in policy and academic discussions, the multi-level governance approach has drawn significant criticism, particularly from scholars aligned with post-structuralist perspectives. A central critique is that this framework is overly rigid, failing to adequately account for non-governmental actors such as social movements, lobby groups, and civil society organizations. From the perspective of actor-network theory, the categories of global, national, and local are viewed not as fixed levels but as outcomes of connections of varying proximities. Latour, for example, asserts that “even the largest organizations, the so-called global players, are just made up of local interactions in the sense that they connect one entity with another.”⁹⁶ Critical urban geographers, such as Faludi, add to this critique by arguing that the concept of territory is a social construct. He contends that the territorial boundaries of local, regional, and national scales are fluid and “do not converge with administrative delineations.”⁹⁷ Instead, Faludi advocates recognizing functional networks that depend on territorial flexibility and “cut across jurisdictions.”⁹⁸ Building on this idea, Janssen-Jansen and Hutton argue that “scale is a dynamic concept, varying by theme and time,” and that “regions will always be constructs ‘in the making,’ defined based on a particular theme or subject around which actors have formed a coalition.”⁹⁹

This subsection challenges the predetermined hierarchies often assumed in multi-level governance models. Instead, it investigates how governance levels are dynamically constructed during periods of economic transition, emphasizing their fluid and context-dependent nature. The three regions examined illustrate significant diversity in these processes. The analysis highlights that in Southeast North Brabant, the national government is the key driver supporting the transition to a knowledge economy, while the EU level has a relatively minor influence. In Cluj, by contrast, the national government provides limited support and at times actively impedes the scaling of IT ecosystems, whereas the EU sets direction and allocates some funding for the development of digital and IT economy, yet its role is not as large as the private entrepreneurs at the local scale. In the Basque Country, the region’s autonomous status enables its regional government to act as the most influential and self-sufficient entity in governing transitions, with the national and EU levels playing largely peripheral roles. The next subsection delves deeper into the factors that shape these varying roles of regional, national, and EU governments across the three regions.

National support comes with its own agenda: the case of Southeast North Brabant

Public administration in the Netherlands operates across four tiers: central government, provinces, municipalities, and water authorities. According to the Global Innovation Index, the Netherlands ranked 8th in innovation outputs in 2024, succeeding Germany, China and Japan.¹⁰⁰ The country boasts two clusters among the top 100 science and technology clusters globally: Amsterdam-Rotterdam (26th) and Eindhoven (42nd), the latter being the capital city of the Brainport region. The Brainport region ranks among the top producers of patents both in Europe and globally, with its intellectual property (IP) and products holding strategic importance for the Netherlands.

Our findings reveal that the national government plays a pivotal role in the region's economic transition. As Europe's leading competitor in chipmaking, the Brainport region presents as a device of power to compete with China and the United States, making national government involvement crucial in shaping its development and policy direction.

Interviews suggest that the concept of "Brainport" was developed strategically to emphasize the region's importance and secure national financing. One interviewee explained, "The concept of Brainport was developed with the idea of getting attention from The Hague." This strategy proved highly effective, particularly under the leadership of a former mayor who had strong connections in The Hague. As another interviewee noted, "It was good when we got Mr. [Name of the previous mayor of Eindhoven] as our mayor because he was well-known in The Hague. He knew how to navigate to the right people, and it worked quite well." (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023).

Through the 2017–2021 **Regio Deal** program, the national government made significant investments in the Brainport region, focusing on:

- Developing the digital ecosystem,
- Attracting international talent,
- Advancing photonics and other emerging technologies.

On November 22, 2023, a new coalition government with a strong anti-immigration stance was elected in the Netherlands. The leader in the chipmaking industry, ASML, threatened to leave the country, citing challenges in attracting the highly skilled talent essential for its operations due to the new government's policies. In response, the national government initiated "Project Beethoven" to persuade ASML to remain in the region. Under this program, the national and regional governments committed a total of €2.51 billion (€1.73 billion from the national government and €778 million from the regional government) to enhance the business environment for the chipmaking industry. The funding is allocated as follows: €1.06 billion for mobility, €425 million for housing, and €1.03 billion for talent development.¹⁰¹

"Of central government's total contribution, €1.28 billion will come from the National Growth Fund. Given the enormous growth potential that the chip industry and Brainport represent, as

well as the positive role that a strong ecosystem can play in terms of addressing national challenges, these investments are in line with the National Growth Fund's purpose of strengthening the Netherlands' future earning potential."

*"The government expects that these measures will lead ASML to continue to invest and base its operations in the Netherlands, including for statutory and tax purposes. The package of measures was designed based on current growth forecasts and investment plans of the semiconductor industry and Brainport Eindhoven. Any changes in these investment plans will result in an adjustment to the forecasts and the requisite public commitment."*¹⁰²

Moreover, the region's economic strength has fueled local ambitions to expand its territorial scale. During his 2017–2022 term, Eindhoven's former mayor, John Jorritsma, advocated for merging 21 municipalities into 4, arguing that the region's economic and social development necessitated economies of scale. He also pursued the ambition of Eindhoven joining the G4—a coalition of the four largest Dutch cities: Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague, and Utrecht.

*"It is time for Brainport Eindhoven to claim the still empty seat of the fifth city of the Netherlands at the government table. But that can only happen if Eindhoven is big enough."*¹⁰³ (Translated from Dutch)

While the mayor's push for merging municipalities focused primarily on economic growth, our interviews revealed that this perspective was also shared by actors in the social domain. One informant from the social sector noted that Eindhoven receives significantly less funding per resident compared to G4 cities, which constrains resources for social services.

"It sounds simple, but making sure you receive the same amount of funding as the G4 is really crucial for the social domain. For example, the difference in per capita funding—whether it's 75 or 105 euros—is substantial. There needs to be a clear agenda for this, because only then can you ensure that everyone participates." (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023).

Despite failed municipal referendums where residents voted against the merger and years of subsequent discussions, the merger has not occurred.

In conclusion, our data shows that the Brainport region, home to major chipmaking producers vital to both the national and EU economies, benefits significantly from national government investments in the R&D ecosystem. The regional government recognizes these opportunities and strategically leverages them to strengthen its position on the national agenda. However, our findings do not indicate a significant role for the EU level in the development of the region's tech ecosystem, suggesting its peripheral influence on the regional transition.

Additionally, our findings indicate that the national government is both directly and indirectly reinforcing the region's pro-growth agenda. Directly, investments are largely aimed at benefiting major chipmaking companies like ASML. While funding directed toward attracting international talent has the potential to exacerbate challenges such as social housing shortages, limited access to social infrastructure (e.g., schools and kindergartens), and growing social polarization between highly skilled international migrants and local residents, some relief is anticipated. Specifically, 1.06 billion euros for mobility and 425 million euros for housing are allocated to improve the quality of life not only for large private company employees but also for other social groups, including the working poor and homeless (for more details on these groups, see Chapter 5). Indirectly, the regional government's desire to strengthen its standing with the national government has driven efforts to pursue municipal merging goals.

European funding and national shortfalls: the case of Cluj County

In contrast to the Netherlands, with its extensive strategies and multi-million-euro investments in the Brainport region's ecosystem, national support for the Cluj ecosystem in Romania is small. Crucial policies and laws that promote knowledge transfer, foster cluster development, and protect intellectual property are lacking. As one senior manager in the IT ecosystem explained: *"There is no national policy for supporting cluster establishment or development. There's nothing in place, nor at the local, regional, or national level."* (Interview, Cluj, 2023). Furthermore, the national government has not enacted laws to protect intellectual property, enabling international companies like Bosch to register patents produced by Romanian employees at the Romanian Bosch branch in Germany. This lack of policy is one reason Romania ranks among the lowest in patent creation.

"We have... for example, Bosch has their research and innovation center. There are hundreds-hundreds of patents created each year here by Romanian people, but they are registered in Germany. [...] but that is because of the lack of legislation in place, because the Romanian legislation does not force the multinational to register here in Romania... The IP created by the Romanian employees." (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

According to the experts we interviewed, funding for Cluj's startup community and digital economy primarily comes from private companies, with additional support from European programs like Digital Europe and European Regional Development Funds.

"Currently, the majority of the projects being implemented even in digital are coming from EU funding not from the local budget. Yeah. The public administration must have a lot of restrictions." (Interview, Cluj, 2023).

The most significant contribution of the national government to the development of Cluj's IT ecosystem has been its tax-exemption policy for IT workers. A study by Manelici and Pantea found that this tax-exemption policy accelerated the growth of Romania's IT sector, a key driver in the transition to a knowledge economy and a source of 'good jobs'—high-paying, high-skilled, relatively stable, and carbon-neutral.¹⁰⁴ However, the national government is now implementing new measures to eliminate these tax exemptions for IT workers, a benefit the community has enjoyed since 2001. This decision follows multiple warnings from the European Commission to reduce Romania's budget deficit, with the risk of losing EU funding.¹⁰⁵ IT sector experts we interviewed expressed concern that the government's actions will significantly hinder the growth of the industry and potentially jeopardize its future. According to one informant:

"It will be a big hit in the IT industry because these companies are in global competition, and they will not be so competitive anymore. [Silence 00:19:47- 00:19:53]." (Interview, Cluj, 2023).

The monopoly of regional scale: the case of Basque Country

Compared to the two cases above, the governance structure in the Basque Country stands out due to its autonomous status, a feature absent in both Romania and the Netherlands. A quote from an interview with one of the informants provides insight into the role of the national government in this autonomous region of Spain:

"[...] We had this system, in which we collect our taxes and pay the state for several services. Those services nowadays are mainly the army, the foreign office, the taxes for things that come from outside - import taxes. Well, just a few things. [...] Every four years, we sign an agreement. Both governments sign an agreement, and we pay an amount of money for that period. To pay for those services that come from the central government, and all the other things are made by us. That's what allowed us to make an industrial policy separate from the policy of the rest of the regions in the state, and in Spain." (Interview, Basque Country, 2024).

Unlike the Brabant case, the Basque Country's financial independence enables the region to plan its own strategies and set its priorities autonomously. As one informant noted, "Yes, because they [the Basque Country] have an independent government, they could promote their policies around industrialization and competitiveness." The region has also established its own laws and policies to stimulate innovation and foster a knowledge economy, including provisions for intellectual property rights, knowledge transfer mechanisms, and multiple industrial, technological, and business strategies. Additionally, policies promoting cluster formations were introduced early on, shortly after the foundation of the Basque Country.

"When the cluster policy was instituted in the 1990's, there was an initial mapping done of the kind of clusters that were present in the Basque Country. Michael Porter's company came and did this mapping." (Interview, Basque Country, 2024).

What makes the Basque Country case particularly stand out is the strong focus of the regional government on promoting a social and wellbeing agenda. At the foundation of the Basque Country are policies that promote the cooperative economy, where employees are the owners of the companies. Additionally, economic growth in the Basque Country is directed toward three social priorities that address current or emerging issues: 1) smart industries, 2) personal health and healthy aging, and 3) the circular economy. For example, the region's natural population change is negative due to declining birth rates and aging. As a result, the government has prioritized healthy aging and personal health as policy goals and economic specializations. These priorities are important in practice because the regional government offers funding and investments in these areas, thereby steering the economy to align with social objectives.

To conclude this sub-chapter on the multi-level governance in transition regions, we can see how different scales position themselves differently in the development of innovation ecosystem. This shows the conflicting roles of national governments that constrains in case of Cluj and steers in case of Brainport (yet reinforces own external agenda). We can also see how, in the former case, the European level appears more prominently under the weak national

government's position, and less prominently under proactive national government, in the latter case. In the case of Basque Country, we can see how the regional level becomes self-sufficient on its own, allowing for long-term economic strategies and strong focus on social wellbeing.

5. EMERGING VULNERABILITIES DURING THE ECONOMIC TRANSITION

During our research, one of our key objectives was to investigate whether the economic transitions in the three regions under study have alleviated or exacerbated socio-economic vulnerabilities. In this section, we present the findings of this investigation in the three regions. The term 'vulnerabilities' refer to the growing socio-economic, political, cultural, or spatial inequalities or challenges faced by these regions. We identified these vulnerabilities through interviews with actors professionally engaged in policymaking, who often have access to extensive data on socio-economic indicators, as well as with residents who shared insights based on their lived experiences in the regions. Where available, we also consulted statistical data and policy documents.

It is important to note that we do not claim a direct correlation between the identified vulnerabilities and the transition policies. We report all significant vulnerabilities found in our data but cannot clearly separate those driven by issues like social inequality and homelessness from those directly caused by economic transitions in these regions. In this chapter, we aim to rely on quantitative data to support our findings on emerging vulnerabilities, where such data is available. We also incorporate dense interview quotes to provide a rich illustration of the experiences of residents from the regions.

Each region, with its distinct starting conditions, implemented policies, and governance approaches, exhibits significant variability in the types of vulnerabilities that arise during the transition process. However, a few vulnerabilities were common across all three regions. We begin by discussing these shared challenges.

Shared vulnerabilities

Housing unaffordability and growing costs of living, especially for young people

Respondents in all three regions highlighted the problem of rapidly increasing costs of living. Even in the Basque Country, which has the strongest social agenda among the three case studies, certain groups of residents struggle to afford a decent standard of living. This issue is particularly pronounced in access to housing but also extends to other essential amenities, such as cars, which are not a luxury but a necessity for mobility in the sprawling region. Research published in December 2024 by the University of Deusto, titled *Deustobarometer Social*, revealed that “access to housing has, for the first time, become the most important problem for Basque citizens.”¹⁰⁶ According to the report, “thirty-one percent of citizens believe that they will never be able to buy a house, and 28% believe it will take more than 10 years.”¹⁰⁷

Our interview findings show that the lack of affordable housing and other costly necessities, such as cars, disproportionately affects young people, including students, who often cannot afford the rents required to study at universities, or access remote jobs in these regions.

“I’m not talking like an expert. I’m talking like, I mean, I see it with my children and especially with my nephews. For them, it’s very difficult to get into a job that they want to. What they earn is ridiculous. It’s always a question for me, and at home, we are changing our car. We have two cars. The smaller car... I was checking the prices, I said, ‘How can my children get one of these?’ I mean, it’s impossible for them. They have to share a home. They can’t buy a house. They have to share rooms with other people. They don’t have cars. It’s terrible.” (Interview, Basque Country, 2024)

“For example, we have a big problem with the price of the dwellings, of the houses. [...] Here it’s so expensive. It’s not ideal with the salaries. I don’t know what is happening. I mean, it’s not coherent, the salaries with the prices. One very important thing is that young people can be independent.” (Interview, Basque Country, 2024)

“The biggest things are of course the problems with the climate. And housing. [...] My youngest one [child] studies in [a city in the Netherlands] and lives in Eindhoven. And she has, I think, something like this [shows a small area] for €300 a month. And it’s not even safe, I think. But anyway...” (Interview, North Brabant, 2023)

In Cluj, the issue of rising housing prices is a significant concern and was frequently mentioned during our interviews. One informant remarked, “Cluj might die from his own success because the price of living here has increased a lot.” As the largest student city in Romania, Cluj is particularly challenging for students, who are among the groups most affected by the lack of affordable housing, as highlighted in the following quote:

“Even the students are having a hard time paying their rent because the places provided by the universities for them to stay are not enough. They have to find their own housing solutions. I know that it’s very difficult.” (Interview, Cluj-Napoca, 2023)

Figure 13 (left) and Figure 14 (right). Performance by young artists in Cluj-Napoca. The poster signs on Figure 12 say: ‘Housing Justice’ and ‘Take Back Spaces’. On Figure 14, yellow and red tape illustrate one square meter of space and are used for a game with the audience.

During our stay in Cluj, we attended an artistic performance by young artists, some of whom were students in Cluj-Napoca. Through their performance (see Figure 13 and 14), the artists highlighted the unaffordability of housing in Cluj, specifically pointing to the disproportionate growth in rental prices compared to local salaries. The artists cited that the average salary in Cluj is approximately 750 euros, while the average rental price per square meter is 8.6 euros, making it more expensive than Bucharest (8.1 euros per square meter), where the average salary is 12% higher. They referred to the *Deloitte Property Index 2023*,¹⁰⁸ published in August 2023, which identifies Cluj-Napoca as the most expensive city in Romania for both buyers and tenants. According to this report, the purchase price in Cluj-Napoca increased by 21.8% in 2023 compared to the previous year.¹⁰⁹

GOOD PRACTICE

Private corporation ASML invests in affordable housing projects in the Brainport region

On December 12, 2024, ASML, the largest private corporation in the Brainport region and the supplier to the semiconductor industry, announced its financial support to deliver 1,085 affordable homes in Veldhoven, Eindhoven and Helmond – the municipalities in which ASML has its campuses. The homes, as the corporation claims, ‘are for the larger part intended for people who are dependent on social housing – not for ASML employees.’ (Source: <https://www.asml.com/en/news/press-releases/2024/asml-collaborates-with-housing-associations>, retrieved on December 30, 2024). The affordable housing projects are led by housing associations together with non-profit organizations and municipalities. ASML will only contribute financially.

The outcomes of this initiative are far from being visible, but such initiative is a rare example of a private corporation contributing to the provision of affordable housing in regions. It is worth mentioning, that according to our interviews, ASML can be considered one of the main actor that contributed to the attraction of large amount of highly-skilled migrants to the region, which led to increased housing prices and lack of affordability in the area. Thus, ASML feels responsible for annihilating its impact. The following quote with one of the policymakers in the Brainport region illustrates this idea:

“And now we’re working very hard to develop a social Brainport agenda, that talks to the companies and addresses them on their social responsibilities also. That their economic growth comes with the cost for the whole region and that they are also partly responsible or should take their responsibility on the effects that they have, for example, on the housing markets, on the social services in the area and on integrating the new employees into the society to keep everything... To keep neighborhoods happy and nice to live in.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

“The ASML affordable housing program is part of the broader sustainability strategy, through which ASML aims to contribute to themes with social relevance. Financial support for these housing projects helps ASML to implement this strategy and at the same time contributes to sustainable growth for the high-tech sector.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

Increasing socio-economic polarization between employees in key economic sectors and other residents

The growing costs of living and lack of affordability in cities significantly influenced by tech industries affect not only those employed in key economic sectors but also other groups of residents. This imbalance in affordability of urban services exacerbates social between these groups. However, the contesting groups of residents vary across the three regions under study.

In Brainport, a region with a strong focus on attracting international talent, polarization is evident between highly skilled migrants and local residents, often referred to as “Eindhovenaars” (Dutch for residents of Eindhoven). A policymaker we interviewed illustrated this tension:

“For example, the expats that come this region in order to work, for example at ASML, all have a very good income level, which is nothing compared to as somebody that works as a nurse. And then if you compete for the same housing, you just see that they [expats] can always offer more, and then the houses go to the expats. And it’s also felt very much by the residents of Eindhoven. And you see that it has a large impact on neighborhoods because you have more expats with different cultural backgrounds moving into neighborhoods. And yeah, also pushing what they call ‘real Eindhovenaars’, [the phrase] which I don’t like at all, but more outside of Eindhoven. Because the housing becomes more and more expensive. There’s very concrete effect.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

Interestingly, although this polarization was a recurring theme in our interviews, it is not supported by official statistical data. Hence, the municipality is working with the so-called ‘perceived polarization’ as a socio-economic indicator, which is based on the opinions of residents. This is how a policymaker explains it:

“It’s something everybody talks about, the gap - they call it - between rich and poor. But we have no proof if that really is, like you said, more prominent in Eindhoven than a different city. I think that’s because of the history of Eindhoven, it is different as a smaller city is growing really fast. It is perceived as such, but we cannot prove it with the data, I should say. So that’s also something that we know we’re trying to find the data. We have immigration numbers, for example, of people coming in. Those data we do have. But we don’t have the poverty and the if that gap is really bigger. [...] Yeah, I don’t like that term. But it does feel like this perceived division, perceived polarization a bit between Eindhovenaars and the expats.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

A Dutch resident in his late 50s, formerly employed in the tech sector but now long-term unemployed, also expressed frustration with perceived discrimination in accessing tech jobs: Here is what he says:

“It is a little bit difficult for me to find a job now. And what I noticed now that’s a lot of... That I believe, I’m not sure, but I think that Eindhoven wants to put on the map for international side and that they make it very easy for people from other countries to come to

Eindhoven to have jobs. That is good from one side, but from the other side...I think they forget their own people. [...] Because for me, it's very difficult to get inside these companies when I solicitate and I really have that's pretty, you know, extensive and I have a lot of certifications. I never get it. I am always denied. Also, I see a lot of people like my neighbor. He's also from America. He works for ASML. He has a good salary. I think I could also do that job easily; you know? So why they don't take me. And you see more and more people in my neighborhood that are not from Eindhoven, but they have very good big cars, big houses. Even after two years they buy a house in a different area. So, they get so much money that they can even buy a house. [...] So, I feel a little bit jealous. Is maybe a big word. But I feel that it's like that Eindhoven is giving more privileges to people that come to Eindhoven than their own people." (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

In Cluj, polarization is also evident between IT workers and residents employed in other sectors. However, unlike in Brainport, the emphasis on international workers is less pronounced, as fewer expats work in Cluj. One informant highlighted the disparity:

"The winners, for sure, are the people working in IT. I'm not that close anymore with the staff from the municipality, but I used to work on a daily basis with them until three years ago. I know they were telling me that at some point, the other people were really hating the people working in IT because they generated this wellness at one part. But also, they determined the increase of the rents, and the prices of the apartments because the Romanian... The Romanians love to buy apartments, not to rent them, but to buy them. [...] The prices went up. In the hospitality industry restaurants are doing really well, but prices are quite high. There is this population that is not involved in IT or who does not have any member working for the IT or related industries, because even the creative industries are very linked to the IT. This might be a very hard time [for them] to afford to live in Cluj." (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

At the same time, some IT workers described their own position as precarious due to the dominance of outsourcing in the industry. As one creative worker in Cluj explained:

"But actually they [IT entrepreneurs] are not doing so well. You may find several interviews done with the IT entrepreneurs in the 2016 issue. When I was also working for the capital of Culture bid and they [IT entrepreneurs] were complaining like hell that we are just slaves of more Western countries like it's outsourcing they don't have their own creative products. They are doing loan type of work, and this is still on today and this is how in the last year, the IT industry still really started to go to hell because the big money just turned away and started to pour in even more poor countries like I don't know, the Moldavia, Ukraine, etcetera." (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

In the Basque Country, our interviews did not reveal significant polarization between employees in key economic sectors and other groups. This could be due to the region's strong social policies, which may mitigate such tensions. However, it is also important to note that fewer interviews were conducted in the Basque Country, meaning the residents' perspectives may not have been fully captured.

Increased polarization of labor market

Another noticeable trend in all three cases is the polarization of the labor market, also known as employment or job polarization. This phenomenon is relatively new and was first documented in academic literature.¹¹⁰ It primarily occurs in labor markets within developed and urbanized countries. Job polarization is characterized by a growing proportion of employment in both low-skilled and high-skilled occupations, accompanied by a decline in middle-skilled jobs.¹¹¹

The primary theoretical explanation for job polarization lies in technological advancements within the labor market. Technological innovations increase demand for high-skilled, non-routine tasks (such as research or medical diagnosis) while simultaneously replacing labor in routine tasks (such as basic problem-solving or machine operation).¹¹² This shift results in a pattern of job polarization, making it particularly pronounced in innovation- and technology-driven regions, such as the three cases under study. In addition to technological change, scholars point to other factors contributing to job polarization. These include outsourcing (relevant in the case of Cluj), increased consumption of goods and services, and growing wage disparities between low- and high-paying jobs.¹¹³

Figure 15. Regional Job Polarization, the Netherlands.
Source: Terzidis et al. (2017).

Our interview data highlights growing concerns among informants about job polarization in all three regions. In the Brainport region, for example, a quantitative study by Terzidis et al., illustrate on Figure 15, confirms that the labor market around Eindhoven is strongly polarized.¹¹⁴

Additionally, a policymaker in Eindhoven expressed concern about the lack of accessible jobs, highlighting the issue of discrimination, which disproportionately affects refugees.

“What you see is that we can improve also the job market or the labor market and make it more accessible to the people who don’t have jobs right now because there’s, for example, discrimination in the internship world. For refugees, it’s harder to find a job or find a good match. I think that a lot can be improved over there as well, but the shortage is not in the number of jobs, but the number of people that can fulfill these vacancies.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

They also emphasized that the availability of jobs in specific sectors, whether highly-skilled or lower-skilled, is ultimately a political choice.

(1) “I think we need to make choices. We cannot do everything. For example, you now have those... A stupid example, but those [Dutch word], like those deliverers on bikes that deliver food within ten minutes. It’s a really stupid example, but do we want to provide this economy, or should we make sure that we have enough people for the energy transition, health care, and so on? We also have to make these kinds of choices.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

(2) “We have a shortage of employees. That’s why a company like ASML attracts more and more people from outside of the country. “This is because we cannot fill these vacancies with people living in the region,” they say. For me, it’s not only the companies, but also the public sector, education, and healthcare.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

In the case of the Basque Country, we did not find quantitative data on labor market polarization. However, our interviews confirm the presence of this phenomenon. For instance, one policymaker explained:

“The problem nowadays here is that the labor market is very polarized, so there are high-qualification jobs and then low-skilled jobs. The gap between a high qualification and a low qualification is bigger. We think that it’s important to identify or to try to add value to the job, even if the job is in a restaurant or a cafeteria. We have to try to introduce technological procedures to improve their skills because the labor market is going to ask for those kinds of skills.” (Interview, Basque Country, 2024)

As they further elaborated, such labor market polarization has led to an increased demand for jobs in IT, while individuals lacking highly specialized skills face long-term unemployment due to the limited availability of low-skilled jobs. This situation creates a paradox: although the labor market reports many open vacancies, these positions often remain unfilled due to a shortage of high-skilled workers, leaving many low-skilled workers unemployed. Interestingly, this informant, similar to those in the Brainport region, highlighted migrants and refugees as a group particularly affected by these labor market challenges:

“Some people have been underqualified. They’ve been there for years and years, and they are not able to get a job. But the labor market says that they need employees. What they need are engineers or IT workers, but our people, who are in poverty, don’t have these kinds of skills. They don’t have education. For example, the people who we work with were very different in the 90s and nowadays, because in the 90s, more of them were people who had been working in the industrial sector. Then with the industrial revolution and the crisis, they lost their jobs. They don’t have a qualification. They had low-level skills or low qualifications. Nowadays, in the 00s, we have the migration. There has been a migration process and most of our people who are in a bad situation socially, come from other countries. There are more difficulties, for example, idiomatic difficulties and cultural. There’s a difference. We have to work with them to integrate into society.” (Interview, Basque Country, 2024)

In regard to the Cluj case study, we did not find the statistical data on job polarization in Romania, however in our interviews the informants notice this process. For example, one of the IT entrepreneurs explains how his salary in IT was disproportionately high:

“[...] For the local ecosystem it [IT jobs] was high paid work. For example, in my first IT job, my first programmer job. I think, one year in my job, I was earning better than my father, who was working for 40 years, at that point. In my first corporate job, I was earning better than my whole family like mother, father and sister - all of them. So, I would say that IT salaries were really big compared to the local median.” (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

One of the representatives of a local NGO notices how the gap between the IT workers and other professionals, especially academic workers has risen, forcing the latter group to move away from the city because they are no longer able to afford it:

“[...] There is a problem for young people who want to stay here. It’s a huge gap between the IT community and the rest of the people. Especially, professors. I’m very worried about professors because they have a maximum of €1000 per month. My wife is a university assistant professor, and she has a bit less than €1000. Can you imagine that high school professors have even less? [...] We want to have good education in Cluj. But those people can’t afford to live in the city. [...] All the people I knew, because it’s so expensive, moved outside. I have no more friends here.” (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

Increasing number of jobs with precarious conditions

Related to the previous issue of job polarization, another problem raised in the cases of Cluj and Eindhoven concerns the increasing number of jobs with precarious working conditions. Our informants reveal that, although IT companies contribute to job creation by requiring a large infrastructure of supporting services—such as catering, coffee machine maintenance, hotel stays, etc.—the jobs created often come with precarious conditions: low salaries, short-term contracts, and no social security benefits. The following quote from a policymaker in Eindhoven provides a clear illustration of this issue:

“And one of the problems, which we have in the big companies like ASML is that they buy a lot of services, for instance the coffee machines, cleaning. It’s bought at lowest price, so people [who] work there, get the minimum wage and that’s it. And they have a year-contract at the max. [...] You have three or four companies, [who] do the bid and the one with...As always there are lot of things, which they ask for: quality and fair wages and so... But in the end, the one with the lowest price gets contract and you know it has to come out of something. So, usually it’s the wage and the labor. And that’s what we see here also. [...] It’s not the people who have a contract with ASML and or the expats who are moving around the world... And if ASML kicks them out after three years, they go to Silicon Valley, or to India, or to China. Yeah, they don’t care. But it’s the people who do all the other things, like cleaning, like the coffee machines, like the canteen, and they’re all outside companies and they get them at the lowest bid.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

Several informants in Brainport also highlighted the problem of polarization, caused by the significant difference in salaries and working conditions for outsourced service jobs in IT companies.

In Cluj, the issue of precarious work is also notably persistent. This precariousness extends not only to the services supporting IT companies but also to the IT entrepreneurs themselves. Around 90% of IT companies in Cluj offer outsourcing services to Western countries.¹¹⁵ According to the ARIES Transilvania study (2017), 72% of local IT companies in Cluj ‘generate only 4% of the total turnover reported at the industry level, which means that despite the fact that in recent years the number of startups has increased, they are still unsustainable and face the problem of finding clients for their projects.’¹¹⁶

Growing homelessness

Another vulnerability documented in both regions—North Brabant and the Basque Country—is the growing issue of homelessness. This problem was raised by several informants during our interviews and is supported by statistical data.

For example, in the Dutch case, according to the CBS (Dutch Central Bureau of Statistics), there were 451 homeless people registered in Eindhoven in 2015. By 2022, this number had risen to 745, and it almost doubled to 890 in 2023 compared to 2015.¹¹⁷ When compared to the national growth of 22.2% between 2015 and 2023 (from 7,200 people in 2015 to 8,800 in 2023)¹¹⁸, the growth in Eindhoven, the capital of the Brainport region, is considered significantly higher.

In Bilbao, the capital of the Basque Country, the number of homeless people is also increasing. Between 2018 and 2022, the number of homeless people identified by Basque authorities rose from 430 to 658. It’s important to note that official data only counts those sleeping on the streets or in shelters, and does not account for hidden or invisible homelessness, particularly among women, who rarely use shelters.¹¹⁹

While the reasons for growing homelessness are complex and interdependent, the lack of affordable housing and rising living costs in both regions are widely recognized as acute contributing factors.¹²⁰ Additionally, the structure of labor markets is also a significant contributor, as highlighted in a study conducted for the European Parliament. Our findings also suggest that, in the Netherlands, labor market discrimination and a lack of low-skilled jobs are notable factors.¹²¹

Working poor as the new type of vulnerable group

The “working poor” refers to people who have jobs but earn wages that are insufficient to maintain a socially acceptable standard of living. The following quote from an interview in the Basque Country provides a snapshot of this group across the three regions.

“Then there are employed people in poverty because there are some jobs that don’t pay...The poor workers, they say. We have been talking before about that. That’s a real problem. Even if they work, they cannot pay the rent or the electricity. They cannot afford to live. There’s a real problem. Even if we are much better than in other places and the public administrations give a lot of money in social services to reduce these differences or this situation, the situation is not good. At least we would like it to be better.” (Interview, Basque Country, 2024)

According to a study by Eurofound, factors contributing to working poverty include low pay, household characteristics, the quality of employment, gender, and other individual characteristics. The study also notes that the working poor “face significantly more social problems than the population as a whole: in-work poverty is associated with lower levels of subjective and mental well-being, problems with accommodation, poorer relationships with others, and feelings of social exclusion.”¹²² While regional data on in-work poverty is rarely available, Eurostat data shows that Romania has the highest rate in Europe, with 15.2% of workers at risk of poverty. Romania is followed by Spain (12.7%) and the Netherlands (5.1%). Interestingly, in-work poverty predominantly affects the young. For instance, in the Netherlands, the share of working poor aged 18-24 is 10.1%, which is twice as high as the share in the 18-64 age group.¹²³

While having a job or increasing the minimum wage might be considered remedies for in-work poverty, our findings suggest that the rising cost of living may contribute as a trigger. Thus, we argue in line with the studies that propose that wage levels alone cannot determine in-work poverty and should always be considered alongside the cost of living, particularly housing prices and utilities.¹²⁴ Some countries, such as the UK, also factor in childcare costs when measuring in-work poverty.¹²⁵

Digital literacy as a mode of exclusion

In both, North Southeast Brabant and Basque County, the exclusion of residents from welfare service provision due to the digitalization of these services was identified as another emerging trend during the transition. An expert from the NGO sector working directly with vulnerable communities in Eindhoven describes the problem as follows:

“Yeah, because everything is digital. You do everything with your ID, and your social number, and things like that. Everything [is] on the computer, on the phone. I don’t know how you call that in English, but the people with the low intelligence, then are the victims now. Absolutely. Because they want to participate, they want to be here, but they all don’t understand.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

In the Basque Country, informants highlight not only digital exclusion due to low digital literacy skills but also the lack of access to essential tools, such as computers and smartphones:

“For example, with this digitalization, the Basque government is making a lot of efforts to digitally light all the processes of public administration. However, our people don’t have a computer or an electronic device or whatever, so they are out of the system. If you don’t take into account that there are people who don’t have those tools, computers, or mobiles, they’re shut out.” (Interview, Basque Country, 2024)

Additionally, one informant in the Brainport region raised an issue that has gained attention in recent years, particularly with the evolution of artificial intelligence (AI): the lack of digital literacy skills needed to identify online scams and misinformation. These scams are becoming increasingly sophisticated, specifically targeting the most vulnerable groups, including individuals with limited digital literacy, disabilities, or those experiencing social isolation, often elderly people.

“ [...] You see on Facebook everything’s OK, everything is wonderful and they try to compare but... If there is someone says I give you a scooter. But you have to do that and that. And with no intelligence, he said yes, I do that. I have scooter. And they become in problem.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

Scammers and disinformation campaigns can erode trust in democratic systems, weaken civic engagement, and deepen the marginalization of digitally excluded groups.¹²⁶ This underscores the urgent need to address digital exclusion and vulnerability, while rethinking these issues in the context of their intersection with marginalization and social vulnerability.

Specific to Southeast North Brabant: problem of political representation

Our data revealed a vulnerability specific to the Dutch case of the Brainport region: an increasing gap between policymakers and residents, resulting in a problem of political representation. This widening gap is acknowledged by both residents and policymakers themselves. For example, one informant with a long political career explained that socioeconomic inequality between policymakers and residents contributes to the representation gap:

“The gap between the people who make the policy and people who live the policy is really big and coming bigger will become bigger. [...] If you ask, let’s say a politician in the Hague or even in Eindhoven what he sees as the problems. How often does he speak to people from those areas or so there, there is a big gap between people who make the business and people who have to live in the environment, but that’s not especially for Eindhoven.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

An informant with extensive experience working with homeless and vulnerable people highlighted another dimension of this political representation gap: it might lead marginalized groups to withdraw not only from political participation but also from economic engagement with society:

“[...] But that is with the trust in the Brainport region, politics and... That’s what I’m concerned about... Things may not go wrong economically, but things do go wrong in terms of confidence in the Brainport region. That awareness is there, but they [Brainport decision makers] don’t have the magic wand about how we can organize this together. [...] And that will hit the vulnerable the hardest, because they will soon no longer want to work, they will immediately no longer trust it, they may... Hey, you can already see it - Covid has also done something to it - that you see more and more people who simply no longer trust the entire government system, which means they no longer pay bills, because they say: ‘I will no longer participate’. And that strengthens - I think - a bit in Brainport, because things are going so fast here, with so many knowledge workers.” (Interview, Eindhoven, 2023)

Studies show that representation gaps contribute to distrust in democracy and the rise of right-wing populist parties.¹²⁷ While this issue persists in nearly all European countries, our data suggests that it is more prominently raised in the Dutch case. This concern was substantiated by the national elections held shortly after our interviews, where, for the first time, the right-wing populist party PVV won the largest number of seats in government, validating the concerns expressed by our informants.

Specific to Cluj County: growing urban-rural divide and discrimination towards Roma communities

A significant vulnerability identified in Cluj County, mentioned by more than half of the informants—including residents, policymakers, entrepreneurs, academics, and NGO specialists—was the growing divide between rural and urban areas. According to our data, this divide is primarily driven by the urban cores that “absorb resources: human resources, and any other type from all around the area” (Interview, Cluj, 2023). For example, one informant described the inequality of school services between Cluj and its surrounding villages:

“We have like 19 villages that are part of the metropolitan area, as we call it. Another 19 villages that do not have too many resources. There are immense differences, I would say. I think it’s just something that happens all over the place, the big urban cities receiving a lot of resources. Also, even a lot of parents that have a bit more income, are deciding to take their kids inside the city in the schools, which means flourishing [schools]. For example, it is like the bedroom of Cluj, as we call it, and is a village next to Cluj. A lot of parents will take their kids from Florești to Cluj. Of course, in Florești, you will have a lower quality of everything from teachers to students.” (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

Many informants referred to Florești as a prominent example of a peripheral area where “people who cannot afford to live in Cluj go to places like this near Cluj, where there is continuous development” (Interview, Cluj, 2024). Some informants even referred to it as a “ghetto of Cluj,” highlighting the stigmatization of this area:

“[...] in many cases, where people sold their apartments in Cluj and bought small apartments in Florești. Have you been there? This is like a village. It was 7,000 people 20 years ago, and now it’s like 50,000. It just looks very ghetto-ish. You can see how the blocks are built on agricultural strips. You had the long strip and then you just have like squeezed ten blocks of flats and then the next strip of land, another ten blocks. Nobody thought of roads, sewage, water, or playgrounds. Any public service at all. Where should we build a school? Should we build a kindergarten? A lot of people migrated, and that’s also something that you don’t see unless you come to the city and say, wow, this is a successful story.” (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

Another informant added to this description:

“That have no plumbing, they have an outhouse, an outdoor toilet, no access to gas lines, and even smaller municipalities, they don’t match the level of socioeconomic development of the city.” (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

The government has recognized the urban-rural divide in the metropolitan area. Through the EU’s Functional Areas program, a regeneration project was implemented in the center of Florești commune and other rural communes. However, instead of prioritizing improvements to public services, connectivity, and housing conditions, the project focuses on traffic restriction and calming measures in a commune suffering from highly transited national and county roads.¹²⁸

While the urban-rural divide is acute in the case of Cluj, it is not unique to the region. According to research conducted for the European Parliament, Romania has the largest rural population in Europe, with over half of its population living in rural areas.¹²⁹ The proportion of the population at risk of poverty is more than 20 percentage points higher in rural areas than in cities, signifying deep inequalities across the country.

Figure 16 (left) and 17 (right): Living conditions of Roma communities in Pata Rat, Cluj-Napoca. Source: Authors.

Another vulnerability identified in Cluj is the social exclusion, discrimination, and segregation of Roma communities. The Roma constitutes the largest minority group in Europe and face entrenched racism in Romania, including forced evictions, segregation in education, systematic exclusion from labor markets, and exposure to verbal and physical assaults. One of the most emblematic forced evictions of a Roma community in Romania occurred in 2010 in Cluj-Napoca.¹³⁰ We would like to describe the process from the perspective on one of the evicted Roma community members:

“This is what happened in 2010. It happened in the middle of the winter. It was December, one week before Christmas. The City Hall considered that our place was no longer in the city. They came with bulldozers and with police and army. You can find all this information on YouTube and on the internet if you want to see the videos and they just demolished our houses, took our stuff, and put it in the garbage trucks. The people were pushed into the buses and were brought to the garbage dump and were left there. Also, what was a really bad experience, it was that they built social housing, but we cannot call them that because it’s just one room, 16m² without heating or running water. They had the audacity of not building those social housing for everybody. We were like 76 families [approximately 350 people], but they just built [it] for 40. Thirty-six families were left outside in the cold. They didn’t care. Nobody cared from the city.” (Interview, Cluj, 2023). *I was one of the unlucky ones who didn’t receive a house from the local authorities. In the first two nights, we stayed outside without sleeping with the other neighbors and started to ask, “What is the right thing to do now, and how can we fight this injustice, and what happened to us?”* (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

Most of the families were relocated to the outskirts of Cluj-Napoca, to Pata Rât—a site on a large garbage and former chemical waste dump¹³¹. Today, many houses there still lack legal status and security of tenure, leaving residents at constant risk of eviction:

“In maybe 10 years, a lot of people died just in my community. It’s not speculation. There is pollution over there and is recognized also by the local authorities that is maybe 100 times more pollution in that area that there is in the city. You have a heavily polluted city. We have a lot of cars and shed a lot of dust and a lot of factories. Still, it is more polluted than the City Center.” (Interview, Cluj, 2023)

After many years of fight for decent housing, the activists from the Roma community of Pata Rat has managed to make some progress. The help came not from the local administration, or the European Union, but from the Norwegian Grants (operated by the Romanian Fund for Social Development).¹³²

GOOD PRACTICE

Finding opportunities in the sea of despair: how Norwegian funded social housing project for evicted Roma communities in Cluj-Napoca

To address the housing challenges faced by the Roma community in Cluj, the local community initiated a housing project funded by Norway Grants, with support from the municipality of Cluj. The project aimed not only to provide housing but also to strengthen community capacities through educational and cultural programs, while combating social exclusion. A total of 75 apartments were secured—73 designated as social housing and two allocated for individuals in urgent need. Beyond housing, the program offers psychological and social assistance to facilitate adaptation to new living conditions, support contractual responsibilities, and ensure proper housing maintenance. Additionally, tutoring programs were established to prevent school dropouts, benefiting Roma children by offering educational support. As part of these efforts, 100 children received essential clothing and shoes, ensuring they could attend school adequately equipped. Various cultural activities further contributed to fostering community cohesion.

The success of this initiative was rooted in the ability of local community organizers to design the project and co-decide its objectives. While Norway Grants provided the necessary funding, initial concerns arose regarding the administrative and organizational capacities of the local organizers, particularly in managing a budget of €3.4 million. To address these concerns, local organizers collaborated with the municipality of Cluj to form an association. The municipality ensured responsible financial governance and provided administrative support, while local organizers retained control over project goals and implementation. This governance model offers a valuable example for similar initiatives, as marginalized communities often lack the administrative expertise to manage complex projects but possess the lived experience necessary to identify and address their own needs effectively. By enabling community actors to define project objectives and oversee implementation while ensuring institutional oversight, such collaborative frameworks can contribute to reducing social inequalities. Furthermore, the association played a critical role in supporting the Roma community in applying for additional funding opportunities.

“Before these projects, the association didn’t have a team who wrote the project. This is a good thing that happened because this association also wrote projects for gender-based violence for migrants, for infrastructure, for building parks, and so on. We did a good thing actually, to revive this association, a good thing also for the city and for the citizens of Cluj, because we respect a lot of the citizens of Cluj, and we want to be part of the society” (Interview, Cluj, 2023).

Specific to Basque Country: strong local identity

The strong local identity rooted in the Basque language and culture is a powerful force for community cohesion and pride, but it can also act as a mechanism of exclusion. While the promotion of the Basque language is essential for preserving cultural heritage, it may inadvertently create barriers for non-native speakers, particularly international talents for knowledge economy and migrants, considering declining natural population. This emphasis on linguistic and cultural preservation could limit the region's ability to fully participate in the globalized open innovation ecosystem, which thrives on diversity, openness, and the exchange of ideas across cultural and linguistic boundaries. Balancing the promotion of local identity with the inclusivity needed for global collaboration is, therefore, a key policy challenge.

In the Basque Country, policymakers are already grappling with the challenge of increasing accessibility to the labor market for migrants and refugees. The efforts are underway through a project aimed at streamlining the recognition of foreign diploma's and facilitating the acquisition of work permits. This initiative seeks to remove bureaucratic hurdles and ensure that skilled migrants and refugees can participate in the local economy. However, balancing these efforts with the region's strong emphasis on preserving the Basque language and culture remains a complex challenge.

6. INNOVATIVE INITIATIVES FROM THREE REGIONS: INSPIRING CASES FOR POLICY- MAKERS

From Southeast North Brabant

Springplank – a chain of homeless shelters that speaks the language of Tech Community

Website: <https://www.springplank.org/>

Description: Springplank is committed to people with various needs and offers a tailor-made route to life security. The organization helps people regain control of their own lives through three pillars: work, housing and a social network. At the start of a route, Springplank stimulates people through their 'Work First' principle. When someone comes to Springplank, they are integrated into work immediately. In addition to that, Springplank provides housing and helps to establish social network to help participating in society again.

Work is our top priority. This means that if someone comes to the shelter, we expect them - and no matter how many problems you have, it doesn't matter - that you will do something the next day.

We have separated the target groups. So, the heavy target group is offered shelter, but so is the less heavy target group. And they are separated from each other - as best as possible [...]. But that means you see that the people with serious problems are grouped together. And in the past, people [who] had big problems and less big problems, they were... how do you say, all in one shelter. And people with less major problems in particular did not do well.

HK1 – a creativity-based community center focusing on reintegration in the society and talent development

Website: <https://www.hkcentra.nl/over-hk1/>

Description: : At HK you can find a wide range of activities and programs that focus on talent development and developing skills. Whether you are interested in creative subjects, technical skills, personal development, or sports activities. The programs are flexible and tailored to the needs of the participants. Whether you are young or old, with or without work experience, you are welcome at HK.

[At HK1, people are] doing duty time... You have to go to prison, and if you don't go to prison you have to do hours here. They think it's very nice if I don't ask: what did you do? What did you do wrong? I don't care. I'm looking at the people now and how they behave now and what they do and what they did sometimes it's important to know, but sometimes not. So, you don't judge too fast.

What I do is guide people through their daytime activities which could be anything, that might be creative activities, but also facility support if needed. A lot of people who come here struggle with some big mental health issues that they need support with. That's where I come in, and I help them by offering activities, by listening, and by transferring to different companies, or other healthcare providers. What we do here is give a more meaningful life or maybe start up for finally getting a job. Maybe a lot of people that come here haven't been working for a long time, so they have to get started again.

From Cluj County

Evocariera - a career counselling service for young people in helping them decide their career path and create it

Website: <https://evocariera.ro/>

Description: Evocariera is a Romanian non-profit organization working with pupils, students, parents, school, and academic professionals. They educate on career management and future of work, as well as inform on career and development opportunities. Most of the funds for Evocariera come from Erasmus projects, but some funding also comes from the City of Cluj, and from private companies who support the NGO.

We did a series of interviews, and we put it on YouTube with professionals from all sorts of fields answering 12 questions. What was important for us was not so much about the specialist saying what is her or his job, but explaining how he or she made the decision and built his or her path professional. For example, explaining to young people that you don't have to be a tenth-grade student to become very good in your field. You can come from a village with not so many resources, but if you do a good job, you can go where you want...

We really want to offer this as a free resource. Everything we do is free for young people. We don't put any price on everything.

Fix - Cluj Innovation & eXperiment Fund

Website: <https://fixcluj.eu/>

Description: FIX Cluj is a community-driven incubation program designed to equip aspiring entrepreneurs with the knowledge, skills, resources, and networks necessary to navigate the start-up journey. This program is funded by the Regional Network - Education Cluster, Association C-EDU, Cluj-Napoca City Hall, and Botnar Foundation, a Swiss philanthropic foundation.

Brain drain is a problem in Cluj, but FIX is good. This is helping because they make young people decide to come back to Cluj.

From Basque Country

Gizatea – Association of integration companies of the Basque Country

Website: <https://www.gizatea.net/>

Description: The aim of Gizatea is to create employment for people with social disadvantages. It is an association of 43 (out of 44 existing in the region) social integration companies in the Basque Country. The social integration companies receive public aid for their social services. The companies have several characteristics. 1) All the enterprises in the network are non-profit. All the benefits from the enterprises are reinvested to create new jobs for people with a disadvantage and to improve the product structures and infrastructures. 2) Behind these enterprises there are always social organizations from the organized civil movements. These social organizations work with disadvantaged people. With the help of the enterprises, disadvantaged people can reintegrate into society through employment. 3) These enterprises are transition enterprises, meaning that the employees cannot be employed there for more than three years. That means that the final aim of the transition company is to help their employees to transit to the regular labor market. 4) Besides offering the employment and vocational training, the enterprises also offer social help to the interpersonal skills and social education. In the recent years, Gizatea has identified three transition sectors where creation of employment opportunities is prioritized to provide the most relevant labor skills: 1) silver economy (e.g. elderly care); 2) circular economy (e.g. waste management); 3) demographic transition.

We have to prepare for real opportunities on the labour market. If we work in a sector where there is no relation with the opportunities on the labour market, the opportunities for our people are going to be lower. This is because they don't have the qualifications or the skills to get a job, if we are working in an emerging sector, and we prepare people to work in that sector, its going to be much easier for them to get a job on the labour market.

Konfekoop - Confederation of cooperative companies of the Basque Country

Website: <https://konfekoop.coop/>

Description: The Basque Country is internationally renowned for its unique and thriving cooperative model, which has become a benchmark for inclusive and democratic business practices around the world. At the heart of this ecosystem stands Konfekoop, the Confederation of Basque Cooperatives. Established in 1996, Konfekoop serves as the official representative body for all cooperatives in the Basque Country, uniting diverse sectors under one umbrella to promote, protect, and advance the values of cooperativism. Konfekoop brings together 1,400 cooperatives, with 60,000 jobs and one and a half million members. By bringing together cooperatives from industry, agriculture, finance, education, and more, Konfekoop fosters a strong collective voice in dialogue with public institutions and plays a key role in shaping economic and social policy in the region. As the central pillar of Basque cooperativism, it exemplifies how solidarity, shared ownership, and democratic governance can drive regional development and innovation.

One of the reasons why we have help up better, among other things, was because of our solidarity system measures. When things go wrong, the cooperative member holds up much more than if it were a commercial company. In a society of another type, one of the measures used to avoid the damage from a crisis is to throw workers out on the street, for example. In our case, we have mechanisms for solidarity between cooperatives, so that cooperatives that are doing well take on workers from other cooperatives that are doing poorly.

We also have mechanisms to lower our salaries. During COVID, we, the cooperatives, would lower our salaries significantly. What we call tightening our belts. We also have other measures of solidarity systems through which, for a certain year, a cooperative that is in a bad situation can receive funds from another cooperative when there is an agreement between them for mutual aid in these cases.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND KEY TAKEAWAYS

In this final chapter of the report, we summarize our findings and key takeaways on how to effectively govern the transition to a new economic base, while ensuring that workers from diverse communities retain their jobs and preserve their quality of life. Our analysis of the three regions under study – Southeast North Brabant, Cluj County, and the Basque Country – reveals a transition from industrial economies to digital, innovation-driven, or knowledge-based economies. This transition appears to be successful when measured by macroeconomic indicators, such as increased GDP and decreased unemployment. However, we have also observed that while economic transition can reinvent a region, attracting capital, jobs, knowledge, and enhancing its attractiveness, it also brings with it a set of challenges.

Our research underscores the importance of a nuanced understanding of the cultural, historical, social, and economic factors that influence policymaking processes. These factors can resurface if not adequately addressed. **Therefore, our first and key recommendation for policymakers considering similar transitions in their regions is to recognize these complexities and avoid one-size-fits-all strategies.**

First, we focused on understanding the roles of government, educational institutions, and civil society, along with, to a lesser extent, the private sector, within the triple-helix governance model, which, as our findings show, was predominantly utilized for governing the transition. The key role of public sector is to protect and stimulate innovation development, transfer and infrastructure with relevant law and policies. The key role of educational institutions is to provide relevant skills for workers, develop and transfer innovations. The key role of the private sector is to invest in developing innovative products and services, provide employment, ensuring profitable business.

Key takeaways about the role of government in transition regions.

- The most important task for government to incentivize knowledge-based economy and innovations by providing an elaborate legal and regulatory base.
- Tax incentives to startup projects and IT workers can help attracting talents.
- Local government in Brainport does not invest in innovations but in the stimulation of programs that foster innovations, acting as a private agent bounded by its public role.
- It is crucial to maintain the government's ability to guide the economy while identifying effective public instruments to strengthen its position relative to the private sector, such as the leasehold system used in the Netherlands.
- It is important to control and steer economic growth in the direction where societal challenges occur or are expected to occur in the future (e.g. policy priorities in Basque Country).

Key takeaways about the role of educational institutions in transition regions:

- The universities are embedded in the wider political context directed by public government. Thus, the amount of public funding for education, salary scales of academic workers, policy frameworks around internationalization of education, knowledge transfer and protection of intellectual property – all this affects the opportunities and constraints of universities to participate in the triple-helix structure.
- Developing a cluster that focuses on promoting university-industry-societal relationships can be a great advantage.
- Physical connectivity is an important aspect of collaboration, bringing educational institutions to industrial campus or vice versa will most likely lead to collaborations.
- Finding the balance between academic and applied education is important for the development of knowledge economy. Secondary vocational schools that provide students with practical skills of producing and creating materials for innovations and technologies should be included as equal partners in the collaborations.
- Societal implications of technical creations are often overlooked, however, experienced professors in the field of innovation development found it a big regret. Thus, it is crucial to include societal actors (often referred as 'end users' by IT professionals) and social scientists in technically focused collaborations from the very beginning to address questions regarding cultural, social and ethical implications of technology. Finding common language can be challenging at first, but embracing differences and utilizing them will give great results. Truly interdisciplinary projects are valued the most by European and international funders.

Key takeaways about the role of civil society in transition regions:

One of the main findings of this report is that civil society is largely excluded from the decision-making in the transition governance and is excluded from the network. Key obstacles include the high complexity and public inaccessibility of firms developing emerging technologies and innovations, the heterogeneity of civil society organizations, and difficulties in effectively representing the sector. Additionally, we identified the lack of experience and capacity among civil society actors in engaging with public policymaking processes. In both Cluj County and Southeast North Brabant, interviewees emphasized the need to strengthen civil society by fostering greater cohesion, enabling it to formulate common interests, and ensuring it can represent the sector on equal footing with the private and government sectors. The triple-helix models, which did not initially include civil society, now face significant challenges in integrating it later in the process. Therefore, it is essential to involve civil society from the very beginning. This inclusion should focus on shaping a shared language, acquiring skills, knowledge, and experience in technological and innovation processes, and leveraging—rather than overlooking—the differences between the business community, public and educational sectors, and civil society.

At the beginning of the research, we posed two main research questions, which we would like to revisit:

1) *What do governance networks in the 'economically successful' transition regions look like? What is the degree of variation between them?*

2) *And to what extent do governance processes of transitions transform social structures and urban spaces?*

Regarding the first question, we found that the governance networks steering the transition to a digital, innovation, or knowledge-based economy in all three regions generally adhered to the triple-helix model. However, significant variation existed across the regions. For instance, Chapter 3 presents visual differences in the model's architecture, while Chapter 4 highlights how the multi-level governance structure differed between the regions, with each governance level performing distinct functions. These variations in governance performance and the roles played by each helix were influenced by the differing capacities of each sector, shaped by the political, geographical, cultural, and economic contexts of the regions in which they were embedded.

Regarding the second question, we found that the regions experienced significant implications across all spheres during the digital transition, which we outlined in Chapter 5. We identified several shared emerging vulnerabilities between the regions, including increasing socio-economic polarization, challenges in access to housing, labor markets, and decent jobs. We also observed the intensification of homelessness, digital exclusion, and the growth of a specific vulnerable group: the working poor. Additionally, each region exhibited distinct vulnerabilities. For example, Southeast North Brabant faced issues with political representation, Cluj County saw a growing urban-rural divide, and the Basque Country struggled with the strong local identity being the obstacle for the local labor market.

Remaining Questions for Policymakers

- What is the ability of government to slow down economic growth in a technological region?
- How to increase the influence of local government on private sector?
- What instruments can be efficient in capturing public value from the ecosystem growth?
- How to open up the Triple-Helix structure to include civil society groups?

Last but not least, our findings clearly indicate a critical trend: if governing bodies continue prioritizing economic growth without simultaneously investing in social services and policies, the result will be a significant escalation of social problems. For instance, our cases illustrate how attracting international talent can lead to pressing issues such as a strained housing market, social fragmentation between local residents and migrants, and overburdened social infrastructure like schools, hospitals, and childcare facilities. The rise of the 'working poor' group underscores the growing socio-economic inequality, highlighting that cities are becoming increasingly unaffordable even for those with full-time employment, with living costs outpacing income growth. **It is imperative for governments in transitioning regions to strike a balance between fostering economic growth and implementing robust social policies, ensuring that economic success benefits the quality of life for underprivileged residents—not just the highly skilled or talented workers.**

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